

CHAPTER ONE

Background and Purpose

The Effect of Rhetorical Organization on Iranian EFL Students' Reading Comprehension and Recall of Information

1.1. Introduction

Reading comprehension can be seen as a process dependent on the interaction of ‘top-down and ‘bottom-up’ processes. An important, but neglected, aspect of this process concerns the effects of rhetorical organization (sharp, 2002). Tracing the rhetorical development of a text means perceiving how, given the raw material, the writer has selected from it, organized it and given it coherence, until it suits his purpose. Although the reader does not pay attention to the rhetorical organization in normal circumstances, it is useful to be able to analyze it. This is particularly helpful to readers who have to tackle involved and difficult texts. If you can identify the principle by which the text is organized and see how the ideas hang together, it is easier to interpret difficult sentences. Readers who cannot do this may find the text resembles a jigsaw puzzle in which the parts can be identified but the way they fit together is obscure, so that the complete picture (i.e., the overall meaning of the text) is never organized (Nuttall, p. 106). Paragraph organization is certainly worth studying, as some patterns occur

CHAPTER ONE: BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

frequently. Recognizing the pattern may enable us to predict the likely values of sentences; and this in turn helps us to interpret difficult ones. However, not all paragraphs display a clear pattern of organization; and within some paragraphs, it is possible to identify more than one organizing principle. Many paragraphs are organized in such non-typical ways; but that does not necessarily make them difficult to understand. Anyhow, knowing how the text is organized enables a reader to follow the argument better, read more selectively and locate more reading information needed for a specific purpose (ibid).

Rhetorical structure which is a complex network of relationships and the way the underlying ideas are organized within a text, can improve comprehension. To understand more clearly what is meant by rhetorical structure, we need to think about the topic of the text, the writer's purpose in writing it and the audience he had in mind. Once you know the topic, purpose and target readers, you can go on to ask how the writer approaches his objective. Answering that question involves tracing the rhetorical development of the text. You would not expect a children's story to have the same sort of structure as a university physics textbook. Equally, two physics textbooks are quite likely to be similar in structure. Readers need to know that choice is possible, and to be able to recognize how a text is organized, since this can help them (through top-down processing) to reach an interpretation.(ibid, pp. 26,27).

For this experiment, I compared the comprehension of five passages and recall of two texts like descriptive and causative for an experimental group (EG) and a control group (CG). It was hypothesized that efficient readers who received explicit instruction (EG) used their knowledge of rhetorical organization to help their reading performance with respect to two differently-organized texts (that is, descriptive and causative). The null hypothesis is that there is not any significant differences in comprehension and recall of the two texts between EG and CG. Moreover, there is not a specific rhetorical organizational type that facilitates comprehension and recall, or text organization as a

CHAPTER ONE: BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

tool cannot improve reading comprehension and recall, and as an approach cannot facilitate the teaching of reading comprehension.

It is possible to teach reading comprehension in a non-native language based on the exploitation of text structure, and making our readers aware of and capable of interpreting the rhetorical information a text presents. The ultimate objective of which is to make readers capable of an intentional processing based on the adequate and effective use of two types of knowledge depending on the reading situation they face: the first, knowledge of semantic relations, that is, how sentences may be joined by comparison, causality, etc., or how paragraphs may express two contrasting ideas; and the second, knowledge of the way these relations are manifested in the text. In other words the lexical, syntactic resources the foreign language employs to express the different semantic relations. This processing implies the procedural capacity to draw on relevant knowledge sources and select information from different levels (linguistic and nonlinguistic) in an adequate way. To learn a language means to learn words and sentences, and also to learn procedures to retrieve and process them. That is, the process of learning needs both declarative and procedural knowledge. In this study the focus will be on the kind of procedural knowledge that relates to comprehension and recall of information: Comprehension involves extracting meaning in the light of all available linguistic cues in combination with the learner's general knowledge of the world. Learners use both top-level (top-down) and bottom-level (bottom-up) comprehension to study which cues to meaning learners use, that is, both levels are necessary to extract meaning from the text. The top-level is constituted by the knowledge system; that is, the schematic knowledge. The bottom-level is constituted by the language system (systemic knowledge) Widdowson (1983).

Eskey (1988), for instance, claims that second language readers need to attend more to 'bottom-up' feature than do first language readers. Eskey's view is based on the incontrovertible fact that the former will have weaker linguistic competence than the latter, and will therefore have less ability to draw on the range of cues—both within and external to the text—which are available to readers in a first language.

For this purpose, it is possible to test the effects of formal schematic (rhetorical organization) by keeping the content of text constant, and at the same time varying the rhetorical organization and having comparable groups of participants process each different rhetorical pattern.

1.2. Statement of the problem

Comprehension of text requires use of skills including word knowledge, syntactic knowledge, knowledge of topic, knowledge of text structure, and cohesion (Pressley and Afflerbach, 1995). The reader's social and cultural values will also influence comprehension and as a result a text may be interpreted differently by different people. Reading may be also seen as a process in which the reader may sequentially deal with letters, words and sentences (a so-called bottom-up approach). At the same time the reader may deal with larger units of text (a top-down approach). In addition, as justified in review of literature, rhetorical organization influences comprehension, but the problem is that the students, teachers, writers and curriculum designers are not aware of the role of rhetorical organization and language proficiency on improvement of recall and reading comprehension. In this study, the researcher wants to indicate the importance of rhetorical organization to help the students with a better recall and comprehension of the text. To investigate this claim I compared the performance of an experimental group with a control group. The former received explicit instruction of rhetorical organization and the latter group received no instruction. It was expected that experimental group preceded over the control group in comprehension and recall of information.

1.3. Research Question and Hypothesis

The present study was an attempt in answering a few questions that pertaining to university students' performance (comprehension and recall of information) on texts with different organizational patterns. The objective of the investigation can be expressed in the following research question:

CHAPTER ONE: BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Does explicit rhetorical organization instruction positively affect comprehension and recall?

The above question can be expressed in terms of the following research hypothesis:

H: Explicit rhetorical organization instruction positively affects recall and comprehension.

The null hypothesis of this study is:

H0: Explicit rhetorical organization instruction does not affect recall and comprehension or affects them negatively.

1.4. Definition of Key Terms and Concepts

In this section, definitions of the terms and concepts that have a key role in present study are presented. The aim of this section is to clarify the scope of the present study and the limits within which the findings of the investigation should be interpreted.

1.4.1. Rhetorical Organization (structure): According to Nuttall (1996, p. 26) coherence depends on many things, including the sequence in which sentences are arranged and the value that each has; each sentence takes its value from the others and in turn helps to give value to them. This complex network of relationships and the way the underlying ideas are organized within a text is its rhetorical structure. To understand clearly what is meant by rhetorical structure, we need to think about the topic of the text, the writer's purpose in writing it and the audience he had in mind. Once you know the topic purpose and target readers and writer's objective that involves tracing the rhetorical development of a text. In fact, it is the logical organization of the text which

CHAPTER ONE: BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

the writer has used to represent the intended meaning. There are five groups of rhetorical patterns in expository text (Armbruster, 1986).

1. Collection of description: a listing of items or ideas where the order of presentation of items is not significant.
2. Comparison/Contrast: a description of similarities or differences between two things.
3. Temporal sequence: a sequential relationship between ideas or events considered in terms of the passage of time.
4. Cause-effect: an interaction between at least two ideas or events, one considered a cause or reason and the other an effect or result.
5. Problem-Solution: this is similar to cause-effect pattern in that two factors interact, one citing a problem, the other a solution to that problem.

1.4.2. Recall protocols: This has been the most common method employed in testing reading comprehension. The procedure is not hampered by possible inference from test items and is more likely to focus on communication between text and reader. The assumption is that recall indicates something about the reader's assimilation and reconstruction of text information and therefore reflects comprehension. It requires that text be divided into idea units.

1.4.3. Idea units: An idea unit is the smallest number of words necessary to express a thought or idea. The subject reads the text and his recall is measured and compared with the number of units in the original text (Gambrel, Pfeiffer and Wilson, 1985).

1.4.4. Language proficiency: A simple classification of proficiency as the "four skills" of listening, speaking, reading and writing, is inadequate. There are four approaches to the phenomenon of language proficiency that include theoretical conception, rating scales, standardized tests, and interlanguage studies. Theoretically-based conceptions of proficiency considers behavioral and linguistic content as proficiency schema which cross-tabulated language skills (auditory comprehension, oral production, reading and writing) with language aspects (phonology, morphology, syntax, and lexicon). Proficiency has been interpreted abstractly as communicative competence and analyzed into (1) grammatical competence, (2) sociolinguistic competence, and (3) strategic competence (i.e., the second language learner's ability to compensate for problem in

CHAPTER ONE: BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

communication). Rating scales offer impressionistic global accounts of different stages of proficiency, or the progression from a basic to near native level of proficiency. Tests are useful in academic learning contexts although they may assess only limited aspects of second language proficiency. Errors are recognized as individual in the development of second language proficiency and the learner's degree of proficiency can legitimately be conceived as a 'system' created by the learner for himself. These four approaches complement each other and serve jointly to develop progressive approximation of a more definitive formulation of proficiency of second language learner (Stern, 1991 pp. 347, 349, 352-354, 357).

1.4.5. Comprehension: It is the process by which a person understands the meaning of written or spoken language. It is measured through listening and reading comprehension abilities that leads to the assessment of language proficiency in a second or foreign language. On the part of listening, comprehension includes involving speech reception at the syntactic, lexical, pragmatic, and discourse level through establishing the context in a communicative framework. The listener must be aware of that framework to be able to recreate the speaker's message. Moreover, the listener should activate the relevant background knowledge and use it to anticipate the ideas the message may contain. Byrnes (1985, cited in Chastain, p. 197) says the act of comprehending is essentially meaning driven, holistic, top-down behavior that is highly selective in the features it incorporates. The implications are that listeners listen for meaning rather than for language. Their approach is to listen to the whole message rather than to individual linguistic components of the message. Thus, they use a top down approach as they seek to recreate the speaker's idea. Concerning reading, comprehension is to read for meaning or to recreate the writer's meaning. It is a productive fashion so as to determine meaning even when some of the words, endings, and patterns are not immediately meaningful. Reading signifies comprehension, and the phrase "reading process" implies an active cognitive system operating on printed materials to arrive at an understanding of the message. The reader's task is to activate background and linguistic knowledge to recreate the writer's intended meaning. Schema theory assumes that reader uses a process of semantic constructivity to create meaning (comprehension) from a written or spoken text, which itself has no meaning (Perkins, 1983). Schema theory also predicts that as readers read, they are able to go beyond the

CHAPTER ONE: BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

words and sentence level to the overall organization and discourse level of the reading because their background knowledge enable them to accept and to predict the way in which the writer has organized the material (Carrell, 1984). In other words, their knowledge of story schemata, or writing patterns, makes it possible for them to use the convention of their language to comprehend the text. Grellet (1981) states that proficient readers do not concentrate on sentences and words, instead they start with global understanding and then work toward comprehension of detailed aspects of the reading. Johnson (1981) found that readers better understand content that is related to their own cultural background. Hudelson (1984, p. 226) maintains, "Even proficient ESL reader recall more from a text based on a foreign culture". Carrell (1984) concludes that each type of writing has its own characteristics and that reading comprehension is therefore influenced by the overall organization of the text as well as by the effects of smaller segments such as sentences and paragraphs.

1.5. Delimitations of the study

Preparing an investigation in this field poses a number of methodological difficulties. The experiment must attempt to isolate rhetorical organization so that comprehension is not affected by other factors, such as the background knowledge of the reader or the lexical or syntactic difficulty of the text. This is clearly not an easy task. Among the problems evident in this area of study are:

- 1) The use of texts which do not take into account readers' background knowledge.
- 2) The sample to be used in this study is quite small and this makes generalization difficult.
- 3) Recall protocols have been commonly used in previous researches and in this research, but the methods by which these protocols should be scored is difficult to be clearly explained.
- 4) This study does not distinguish between the genders, whether male readers are more talent in comprehension and production based on the recognition of rhetorical organization or females.

- 5) Making learners aware of rhetorical organization of the text, in reading course limits learners to follow extensive reading.

1.6. Significant of the study

This study indicated that method of teaching reading comprehension and recall of information can be improved through considering structure of the text. This result may be of benefit for both theoretical and pedagogical consideration. Theoreticians may come up with new and better methods for teaching reading, or recall of information, and practitioners may see more organization of the text as an important factor in reading comprehension. This study is of pedagogical and practical importance. This issue is also significant to those who are involved in material selection and preparation for the reading skill.

If convincing evidence is found that text arrangement with the so-called rhetorical organization, is helpful in increasing comprehension and retrieval, teachers and university instructors will benefit from the results. They will present their content materials based on such a hypothesis to facilitate the comprehension and recall of the idea units covered, in other words, if it happens that the outcome of this research reveals any significant difference between the amounts of idea units recalled from the passages awareness of rhetorical organization, text preparation and content presentation should follow the findings by providing readers with texts in such orders of rhetorical organization which enhance later retrieval of the idea units of the texts.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

2-1. Introduction

Chapter one discussed the fundamental issues of this thesis. It provided the reader with a lot of information about some indispensable matters such as: rhetorical organization, recall of information, reading comprehension, statement of problem, question and hypothesis, definition of key terms and concepts, delimitations of the study, and significant of the study. In this chapter, which focuses on the previous background of the study as well as on the review of the related literature, the researcher will be

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

endeavoring to offer a comprehensive background of the question that has gone under investigation by this study and to review the previous researches or studies that have taken different aspects of the problem and have investigated them from various perspectives. With such a purpose in mind, the researcher will present an in-depth discussion on the historical trend that has led to the research problem that has been tackled by this study; also, he will concern two aspects of research. One is reading comprehension, and the other is recall of information. It aims to determine the effect of teaching rhetorical organization on EFL students reading comprehension and recall of information. In this chapter, I review reading comprehension and recall of information in relation to the rhetorical organization.

2-2. Rhetoric

2-2.1. Classical rhetoric

Etymologically, rhetor is a public speaker, whose characteristic art is that of addressing courts of law and popular assemblies. The implications of the original meaning of the word 'rhetor' can be as follows: there is an audience which is addressed by the orator, and an orator tries to influence, persuade or instruct the audience. In a broader scope rhetor is a person "skilled in speaking who addresses a public audience in order to make an impact on it" (Dixon, 1971, pp. 1-2)

Rhetoric as the art of public oratory was one of the seven liberal arts of sciences taught in medieval Europe. These were rhetoric, grammar, logic (dialectics), arithmetic, geometry, astronomy, and music (O'sullivan, Hartley, Saunders, Montgomery, and Fiske, 1994, p. 266). What has been given in many sources as the definition of rhetoric almost support the classical notion of rhetoric. For example, in Asher and Simpson (1994), Crystal (1992), and O'Sullivan et al. (1994), rhetoric is defined as the art of oratory or persuasive speaking. Moreover, some other scholars have defined rhetoric in a more restricted scope as those "tropes and figures of speech, those graces of style and

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

patterns of words which most obviously display an author's 'verbal skill and resourcefulness" (Dixon, 1971, p. 4).

2-2.2. New rhetoric

With the political, social, and intellectual changes of the 17th century, rhetoric began to lose its gleam and vigor to the extent that in the first decades of the 20 century it was regarded by some scholars as the "empty, insincere declarations" (Dixon, 1971, pp. 4-5). Moreover, with the emergence of Audio lingual method, which placed prime emphasis on oral skills, little attention was paid to writing and thus rhetoric (Kaplan, 1988, p. 276). In 1950's and early 1960's no serious study was devoted to "writing dysfunction, nonliterary discourse, construction of the text, or the political and social context of writing" (Lauer, 1993, 45-46).

The exact date of the emergence of new rhetoric is not unanimously determined in the books which have been written on the history of the New Rhetoric or New Composition. Different dates have been mentioned by different scholars. For instance, Kaplan (1988) said that in early 1960's some teachers gradually found that audio lingual method was not able to meet all the needs of the students, specially those who were attending colleges or universities. Consequently, more attention was paid to written discourse and teaching writing (p. 276). Berlin (1987) regarded the breakout of the space race in 1975 as the date of the new rhetoric; he believed "the space race signaled by the launching of Sputnik in 1957 eventually led to federal funds being invested in the teaching of literature and composition for the first time in American history" (cited in Young & Goggin, 1993, p. 23). The date of the meeting of the Conference on College Composition and Communication in 1963 and the date of the publication of such books as The Rhetorical of Fiction by Wayne C. Booth in 1961 and Classical Rhetorical of the Modern student by Edward P. J. Corbett in 1965 are among several dates which are considered as the possible dates of the new rhetoric. And since determining any exact date for the emergence of the new rhetorical is arbitrary, the

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

years between 1950 and 1965 are considered as the period during which the new rhetoric most probably emerged and developed (Young and Goggin, 1993, pp. 22_26).

New rhetoric has been consider and defined from different perspectives. For instance, Flower (1993) consider new rhetoric "as not just a tool for communication or persuasion narrowly considered but as a method of inquiry and as a process of social individual meaning _ making " (p. 171). Another definition, pose by Scott (1993), read as follows:

Rhetorical may be taken as practice, theory, or pedagogy_ and no doubt on a multitude of other ways. As practice, it is endemic. We are awash in a flood of messages designed to maintain or modify patterns of behavior. As theory, Western peoples, at least, have been fascinated in trying to understand the principles that generate eloquent rhetoric and disgusted by the seeming knack of unprincipled persons who abuse their patience. As pedagogy, handbooks and teachers seek to bring theory and practice together will quicken effective performance (p. 121).

Then Scott (1993) continues that the ordinary definition of rhetoric as the art of effective expression gives a very limited picture of the new rhetoric (p. 121). Therefore, the new rhetoric, at least in two ways, has differed from rhetorical work in classics:

First, it [has] studied new subjects and issues including written discourse, writing pedagogy, broader discursive conceptions than persuasion, developmental problems, and writing processes ... [it has] created new theories to explain writing of all kinds_ expressive, expository, persuasive, and literary. Second, this new rhetoric [has] used multiple modes of inquiry, doing reversionary histories of traditional rhetorical texts, creating new theories of discourse, informed by other fields such as psychology, linguistics, anthropology, and recently by literary theory and cultural studies, and conducting a range of empirical studies on problems of literacy (Lauer, 1993, p. 45).

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

The emergence of the new rhetoric and the multimodality of research in this field were most probably due to the problems of written discourse which were overlooked in the 1950's and early 1960's. In this period two main trends in the study of rhetoric gained force: generative rhetoric and contrastive rhetoric. Generative rhetoric developed under the influence of Noam Chomsky's transformational generative grammar. It was a reaction against the organicist position held by Ohnmann who said, "a difference in form always entailed a difference in meaning" (cited in Malmkjar, 1990, p. 383). Conversely, Chomsky argued that one common deep structure, for example, was shared by an active sentence and its passive version. In other words, the same idea can be expressed through different syntactic structures. Later generative rhetoric lost its significance as a field of study, and it developed into a new branch of linguistics called text linguistics. Contrastive rhetoric emerged from Sapir and Whorf hypothesis according to which the different languages reflect differences in the habitual patterns of thought of their speakers. This idea was modified by the forerunners of contrastive rhetoric such as Diane Houghton and Robert Kaplan (Malmkjar, 1990, pp. 382-383). Kaplan (1966) believed:

Each language and each culture has a paragraph order unique to itself and....part of the learning of a particular language in the mastering of its logical system..... In the teaching of paragraph structure to foreign students, whether in terms of reading or in terms of composition, the teacher must be himself aware of these differences and he must make these differences overtly apparent to his students(cited in Maftoon, 1979, p. 13).

Being concerned with the peculiarities of written discourse in each culture, scholars such as Young, Becker, and Pike (1970) defined rhetoric as a field of study which is concerned primarily with a creative process that includes all the choices a writer makes from his earliest tentative explorations of a problem in what has been called the prewriting stage of the writing process, through choices in arrangement and strategy for

a particular audience, to the final editing of the final draft (cited in Maftoon, 1979, p. 9).

2-3. Reading comprehension

Reading is a complex process in which competent readers orchestrate a number of knowledge sources using a variety of strategies to comprehend what they read. These knowledge sources include what Smith (1994) refers to as "visual information" which involves awareness of linguistic and print conventions, as well as "non-visual information" which includes the knowledge that readers bring to the process of reading. In their attempts to make sense of what they read, readers resort to a number of strategies, which are deliberate, conscious plans readers execute when processing textual information. These strategies (e.g., previewing text, using headings and sub-headings, reading, evaluating understanding, etc.) enable them to interpret printed information quickly and efficiently (Feng, 1998, p. 1).

The comprehension of text requires the use of skills including word knowledge, syntactic knowledge, knowledge of topic, knowledge of text structure, and cohesion (Sharp, 2002, p. 1). Sharp (2002) said, the readers' social and cultural values will also influence comprehension as a result a text may be interpreted differently by different people. Reading may also be seen as a process in which the reader may sequentially deal with letters, words and sentences (a so-called bottom-up approach, essentially text driven). At the same time the reader may deal with larger units of text (a top-down approach, more likely to be reader oriented). In addition, rhetorical patterns or structures influence comprehension. A rhetorical pattern is part of the macrostructure of a text and it contains the logical organization of text which the writer has used to represent the intended meaning (ibid:1).

Moreover, reading comprehension has been focused in a variety of disciplines including anthropology, psychology, education, linguistics, artificial intelligence,

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

cognitive and metacognitive approaches. Each of these fields views reading and comprehension from the perspective of its own interests. Educators and some applied linguists, for example, focus more on reading skills, while psychologists, artificial intelligence researchers and some linguists mainly concentrate on cognitive processes involving in reading. Apart from these two general perspectives, reading processes are examined in terms of other variables such as reader's purpose for reading (Gibson and Levin, 1975; Just and Carpenter, 1980), type of information being read, readers' interest and structural features of the text (Rothkopf, 1972; Van Dijk and Kintsch, 1983). In turn, these differences in focus to reading have led to different interpretation of the term 'reading' which can cause much confusion.

Reading was once viewed as a passive skill because the reader does not produce messages in the same sense as a speaker or writer does. Reading, however, as Chastain puts it “requires active mental processing for communication to occur” (1988; p.216). Chastain (1988: 221) said some theorists believe that meaning resides in the text itself; Others maintain that meaning is the product of reader's interacting with the text. In short, some believe that text-based factors determine meaning, while others believe that inside-the-head factors determine meaning (Bernhardt, 1984, cited in Chastain,1988, p. 221). The inside-the-head view implies that reading comprehension rests primarily on the students' knowledge base and that students should therefore read materials that their background knowledge permits them to comprehend. The text-based approach is referred to as bottom-up processing, and inside-the-head model is referred to as top-down processing. (Chastain,1988, p. 221). Widdowson (1979) defines reading as "the process of getting linguistic information via print". This definition according to Alderson and Urquhart (1984, p. 24) is "too general and all-embracing to be of much practical value". Commenting on the issue, Urquhart (1992, p. 1) tries to present an understanding of reading which can be of help to testers. He said:

To talk about reading in terms of getting information from text is to encourage testers in the all too prevalent belief that the outcomes of

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

reading are always measurable. If we define reading as 'purposeful interaction with the print', we may have slipped into jargon, but at least we may keep in mind that the legitimate boundaries of reading tests may be much narrower than reading itself.

Sanders, Spooren and Noordman (1992, p. 1), who developed a taxonomy of coherence relations of text, consider understanding of discourse as "the construction of a mental representation by the reader." Weaver and Kintsch (1991: 237) require a considerable amount of knowledge activating for understanding. They believe that discourse comprehension "requires not only a large set of processing strategies, ranging from the perceptual level to the linguistic and discourse level, but also quite specific content knowledge in the domain of the text" (1991, p. 237). Mann and Thompson (1988, p. 260) argue that "recognition of rhetorical relation of a text which isthe basis of its coherence, is essential to understanding the text." The rhetorical relations that Mann and Thompson (1988) introduced embody the writer's intention in the text and the effect that the writer expects of the readers. These views on reading clearly demonstrate the readers' crucial task in interacting with the text and the writer in their meaning making activity.

Following the above comments on reading, Nuttall (1996, p. 4) assumed that reading has one overriding purpose: to get meaning from a text or reading means getting out of the text as nearly as possible the message the writer put into it. He added that the reader and the writer should have certain things in common if communication is to take place. The minimum requirement is that they have a code (i.e language): that they write and understand the same language. They should have in common a similar command of the language. Moreover, the reader and the writer should have certain assumptions about the world and the way it works: if the writer expects the reader to have a basic understanding of chemistry, the text will not be readily understood by someone who lacks this. The last point is a match between the presuppositions of the writer and those of the reader (ibid, p. 6).He maintained reading is an interactive process as conversation

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

is because both reader and writer depend on one another. The interaction is complicated by the fact that the writer is absent at the time of reading; so she gets no feedback and cannot know what part of her text will cause misunderstanding. She has to guess and shape the text accordingly, but as she never knows who the readers will be, she will never completely succeed. Readers whose language and background differ from the writer's can expect a more difficult task. On the other hand, if they are similar, the reader is likely to interpret the text without conscious effort. A reader who shares many of the writer's presuppositions will be able to think along with the writer and use his own experience to resolve difficulties. He may even find the text so predictable that he hardly needs to read at all. And occasionally, his presuppositions may lead him astray, to force an interpretation that is not in the text. Prediction is important because it activates schemata: that is, it calls into mind any experiences and associated knowledge that we already have about the topic of the text. (ibid, p. 11,13).

Richards and Renandya (2002, p. 277) stated reading for comprehension is the primary purpose for reading; raising student awareness of main ideas in a text and exploring the organization of text are essential for good comprehension. They added formal aspects of language and genre structure contribute to reader's developing comprehension and inferencing abilities. Awareness of text structure is a critical aspect of reading comprehension and learners who are aware of text structure have better comprehension abilities (ibid, 279). Caverly (1997, p. 2) stated that in order to help the students, we should teach the specific reading techniques which are based on the principles we have learned about reading and learning. He refers to these principles as follows:

1. The reader makes a contribution to the teaching process.
2. Word recognition is necessary but not sufficient.
3. There is strong correlation between vocabulary development and reading comprehension. However, developing vocabulary does not necessarily improve reading comprehension.

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

4. Students' interest in, motivation for, and attitude toward reading is vital for success, but we know little about it.
5. Text is organized into super-ordinate, co-ordinate, and sub-ordinate ideas.
6. Text has a variety of relationships that can be taught to improve comprehension.
7. Reading in a study situation is as much a strategic process as it is a comprehension process.
8. Good readers use metacognitive strategies to prepare for, monitor and assess their progress.
9. Strategic reading must vary depending on the task demands.

The aforementioned description and definition of reading suggest that reading is very complex and according to psycholinguistic model of reading it is process-based not product-oriented (Chastain, 1988, p. 222). And that it cannot simply be taught in one or two courses. Since reading is such a complex process researchers have attempted to explain the nature of reading process by analyzing it into a set of component skills. Just like the other three language skills, (i.e., listening, speaking and writing), reading is composed of some components. In order for a reader to comprehend a text, he must have the required mastery over the components. Grabe (1997) mentioned the central components of reading as follows:

Orthographic processing, phonological coding, word recognition (lexical access), working memory activation, sentence parsing, propositional integration, propositional text-model formation, comprehension strategy use, inference making, text model development, and development of appropriate situation model (or mental model) (p. 9).

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Garbe (1991) specified two main approaches to the study of reading: the first one, the component skill approach, counts at least six general component skills and knowledge areas having an impact on the process of reading (p.379):

1. Automatic recognition skills
2. Vocabulary and structural knowledge
3. Formal discourse structure knowledge
4. Content/world background knowledge
5. Synthesis and evaluation skills/strategies
6. Metacognitive knowledge and skills/monitoring

These component skills constitute the sources for defining reading comprehension and specifying the reader's task. Separating the sub-skills in a reading task is however, a matter of controversy. Hudson (1991, p. 83), for example believed "simultaneous application of elements such as content and purpose along with knowledge of grammar, content, vocabulary, discourse conventions, graphic knowledge, and metacognitive awareness" are involve in constructing an appropriate meaning in the text. Mitchell (1987, p. 601) also maintained that "readers must do more than identifying the individual words in the sentence. They must compute all the structural relationships between them" in order to comprehend the text.

The second approach that Grabe sets to interpret the reading process by means of "simple controlling metaphors", (Grabe, p.383) including bottom-up, top-down and interactive processing. The reading models proposed by this approach were under the influence of the theories prevalent at the time of their development. During the heyday of behaviorism, before mid-1960s, little attention was paid to what went on in the mind during the process of comprehension. The emphasis was on observable event external to the individual. "The model attempted to describe how stimuli, such as printed words and word-recognition responses, become associated" (Samuels and Kamil, 1988, p.25). After mid-1960's, with the emergence of cognitive psychology, more attention was

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

paid to mental processes such as memory and attention. The models proposed at that time attempted to describe the process of comprehension through a conceptual network. Even during this same period, the models underwent many changes. Models of 1970's tended to be linear information processing models, where as later models tended to be interactive "with opportunities for feedback loops from components in the later stages to influence components in the earlier stages" (Samuels and Kamil, 1988, p. 25).

The investigation of reading for the purpose of developing models of the reading process that computes the entire reading processes from the contact of the eyes with the graphics of the written language to meaning construction from the whole text traces back to the early 1960s. During this period, as Silberstein (1987, pp. 28-35) documented, the understanding of reading changed. However, Weaver and Kintsch (1991:230) pointed out "it is fair to say that the scientific study of reading and comprehension is still in its relative infancy". Klapp (1992:27) also stated that "no one definitive theory (of reading comprehension) has yet emerged". Samuels and Kamil (1988) extend this view to the models of reading process. They claimed that while research on reading has a history of more than a hundred years, there is still no "strong tradition of attempting to conceptualize knowledge and theory about the reading process in the form of explicit reading model" (Samuels and Kamil, 1988: 22).

Reading comprehension in foreign language education was regarded as a tool for language instruction, examining grammar and vocabulary and practicing pronunciation in mid to late 1960s. In the early 1970s, the emphasis shifted to advanced reading, as Grabe (1991; 736) maintained, without a firm theoretical basis to direct the practice. In the mid 1970s, the importance of reading in language education was documented (Eskey, 1973). In the late 1970s reading researchers felt a need for a theory of reading based on Goodman (1967, 1985) and Smith (1971, 1979). In the 1980s, Goodman's and Smith's theories of reading were expanded (cf. Bernhardt, 1991) to include the integrative approaches to reading that emphasize a triangular interaction among the reader, writer and text.

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

In general, a few outstanding works marked the beginning of a new series of attempts to investigate reading comprehension. These landmarks as Orasanu and Penny (1986, pp. 11-29) outlined are:

1. Chomsky's (1959) review of Skinner's (1957) *Verbal behavior* directed the focus of language research from lower levels such as morpheme and words, to the sentence level. George Miller's (1965) assertion that meaning of a sentence is not equivalent to the aggregation of its constituent word meanings shattered the foundation of behaviorism and signaled the beginning of a new era of investigating language and language learning.
2. Miller's (1956) research inspired the researchers to examine how information is organized in memory.
3. Bruner's (1957) work concerned the development of the mind. Bruner's study laid the foundation of understanding reading as an inferential process.
4. Miller and Selfridge's (1950) study that examined "the contribution of prior knowledge to the perceptive and organization of information in memory,...led to the investigation of the interactive nature of the reading process" (Orasanu and Penny, 1986, p. 5).
5. Interest in the study of language in units larger than single sentences directed researchers to examine "discourse structure, information integration, inferencing, cohesion and schema theory" (ibid).

In addition to the factors listed above, the new trends of linguistic inquiry innovated by Hymes (1972) contended that the social and cultural factors of the language users influence the conventions of text production and text comprehension. The previously developed meaning structures which arose as a result of culturally motivated interaction with the individual's social and physical environment, are the bases of language system for transmitting meanings. Social factors, e.g. cultural presuppositions and cultural frame of reference, according to this view, should not be disregarded in the

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

investigation of language processing strategies as the connection between these conventions and language development is inherent, strong and essentially inseparable. This view of language processing motivated a good number of studies that examined the correspondence between culturally mediated knowledge and processing text (Tannen, 1979).

The concept of reading as an interactive process between the reader and the printed page during which the reader activates relevant schemata to recreate the author's meaning has resulted in a different reading model that uses different criteria to measure readability. The two most important are background knowledge and interest, found by Baldwin et al. (1984, qtd in Chastain, 1988, p. 232). To be separate factors in reading comprehension. In addition to the component skills approach to reading process, three other reading models have also been proposed describing reading comprehension and interpreting the writer's intention in the text. The following section describe these three models.

2-4.1. Bottom-up and top-down models of reading

The examination of the cognitive process involved in reading comprehension was accelerated by the "advent of what has to be known as the psycholinguistic perspective" (Samuels and Kamil, 1988: 22). This resulted in modeling the processes of capturing various pieces of information from the text at various levels of reading comprehension. These models were influenced by the dominant school of psychology in particular historical context (ibid: 25), and can be grouped as bottom-up, top-down, and interactive models.

Earlier work in second language reading assumed a bottom-up (or text-driven) view of reading claiming that "the page bring more information to the reader than the reader brings to the page" (Strange, 1980, p.392). Bottom-up processing, following Carrell

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

(1988a), is decoding individual linguistic units (letters and words) and building textual meaning from the smallest units to the largest (phrases, clauses, intersentential linkage).

According to Stanovich (1980), cited in Samuel and Kamil (1988, p. 31), "bottom-up reading models had a tendency to depict the information flow in a series of discrete stages, with each stage transforming and then passing the recorded information to the next higher stage for additional transformation and recording." An important shortcoming of these models was lack of feedback. There was no mechanism to allow for later processing stage to influence the earlier processes. Also, these views ignored the role of the reader's background knowledge or schemata in the process of reading comprehension.

The bottom-up model primarily organized from behaviorism that views reading as a set of habitual and mechanical responses to written stimuli. It viewed as a linear process in which the reader perceives linguistic inputs, i.e. graphic symbols, and understands the lexical items from the reading material serially. This approach is also referred to as data-driven or text-driven approach (LaBerge and Samuels, 1974; Samuels, 1977).

As it can be understood from the bottom-up view, the implications for reading instruction are that students need to begin reading by learning the letter names, associating the letter names with their sounds, and then be shown how to blend these sounds together into words.

Other second language specialists began to view reading as an active process in which the second language reader is an active information processor who predicts while sampling only part of the actual text. Byrnes (1985) poses that "the act of comprehension is essentially meaning-driven, holistic, top-down behavior that is highly selective in the features it incorporates" (Cited in Chastain, 1988, p. 223). Thus, top-down (or concept driven) views of reading were proposed regarding reading as a

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

process of “making predictions about the text based on experience or background knowledge and then checking the text for confirmation or refutation of those predictions” (Carrell, 1988a, p. 101). These approaches emphasize the role that preexisting knowledge plays in comprehension process and, following Clarke and Silberstein (1977), admit that “more information is contributed by the reader than by the print on the page” (p. 75).a 16-17

In the top-down model the reader starts with a pre-existing structure like a schema and tries to fit the text proposition into it. In other words, the reader actively employs his/her prior knowledge to comprehend the text firstly by making predictions about the text and then by verifying the text for confirmation or refutation of those predictions. This approach is also known as the concept driven or hypothesis driven process (Goodman, 1967,1970; Smith, 1982).

Goodman (1967) describes reading as “a psychological guessing game.” He situates reading “within the broader context of communicative meaning-seeking information processing” (cited in Carrell, Devine & Eskey, 1988, p.20), emphasizing both the psycholinguistic and sociolinguistic aspects of reading. He held:

Reading is a selective process. It involves partial use of available minimal language cues selected from perceptual input on the basis of reader’s expectations. Efficient reading does not result from precise perception and identification of all elements, but from skill in selecting the fewest productive cues necessary to produce guesses that are right the first time

(Goodman, 1967, Cited. in Chastain, 1988, p.223)

He argued that fluent reading is dependent to a considerable degree on the reader's ability to exploit redundancies in the text to reduce uncertainty. By using his or her knowledge of the graphemic, morphophonemic, syntactic, and semantic rules, the reader samples the text and meaning and interprets it in the light of this contextual-

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

pragmatic knowledge of the situation, the function of the text, and intentions of the writer (Goodman, 1967, cited in Celce-Murcia & McIntosh, 1979, p.156).

Alderson (2000: 17) stated that "...much research has emphasized the importance in reading of the knowledge that reader brings to the text." This might seem obvious in the case of L1 reading. However, it is important for learners acquiring an L2 to gain awareness that, even though their knowledge of the new language may be limited, they can still draw on their knowledge of the reading and their topic in hand. According to Goodman (1982) quoted in Alderson (2000; 07) "reading is a 'psycholinguistic guessing game' in which readers guess or predict the text's meaning on the basis of minimal textual information".

Hudson (1988, p.186) reports from Smith (1971), "the reader is not moving from words to meaning, but rather is moving from meaning to words." The basic strategy in reading is, thus, considered to be "reduction of uncertainty, with the reader 'touching as few bases as necessary' (ibid). In the same way, Goodman argues that "fluent reading is dependent to a considerable degree on the reader's ability to exploit redundancies in the text to reduce uncertainty" (in Gorman, 1979, p. 156). T M 17

In line with the above viewpoints, the difference between bottom-up and top-down models is that bottom-up models start with the printed stimuli and work their way up to higher level stages, whereas top-down models start with hypotheses and predications and attempt to verify them by working down to the printed stimuli. Strange (1980) referred to a number of reasons put forth by Rystrom (1977) to discuss why neither view can provide an adequate description. In an exclusively bottom-up view of reading, "there would be no disagreement about the meaning of a text. In addition, there would

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

be no possibility of personal interpretations based on differences such as preconception, age, experience, occupation, etc" (p. 393).

On the other hand, if reading were exclusively top-down, "It would be highly unlikely that any two people would read the same text and arrive at the same general conclusion. It is also unlikely that we would learn anything new from texts if we relied solely on our prior knowledge" (p. 392). Samuels and Kamil (1988), also referred to some of the problems of a top-down model. They say, "For many texts, the reader has little knowledge of the topic and can not generate predictions" (p. 32). Moreover, it may take more time for a skilled reader to form a prediction than simply recognize the words. Top-down models tend to emphasize such higher level skills as prediction of meaning by means of certain kinds of background knowledge at the expense of lower level skills.

Further investigation of reading process suggests the interaction of lower and higher levels of reading process (Carrell, 1988, 1989; Eskey, 1986). Readers comprehend the text by combining the information from two sources: linguistic information in the actual text or from the reading material, and from previous knowledge on context, content, word, etc. Consequently, interactive models of reading were proposed. Eskey and Grabe (1988, p. 26) acknowledged that "interactive models grant far more importance to perceptual processing--that is, the rapid, accurate identification of features at various formal levels --than do strictly top-down models."

2-4.2. Interactive models of reading

The term "interactive", as Grabe (1991: 383) pointed out can refer to two complementary perspectives: (a) The general interaction between the reader and the text where the reader uses his/her prior knowledge and knowledge she/he derives from the text to reconstruct the information of the text (Barnett, 1989; Carrell and Eisterhold, 1983). (b) The simultaneous interaction between lower level skills, i.e. identification

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

skills, and higher level comprehension and interpretation (Carrell, 1988,1989; Eskey and Grabe, 1988; Samuels and Kamil, 1984).

It seems, as Garner (1987) contended, that application of bottom-up, top-down, or interactive approaches varies from reader to reader and from text to text, as readers themselves differ from one another; in their purpose in reading, in their understanding of the topic of the text, in their skill to process the text, etc. Therefore, it appears that readers themselves determine, consciously, which approach to follow and how to process the information in the text. Moreover, the approach the readers follow varies in accordance with the text type. Garner (1987: 3) believed "for simple stories, for which substantial prior knowledge and predictable text structure are the norm, reliance on top-down processing is usually appropriate. For technical prose, on the other hand, in which expectations and structural constraints are less pronounced, reliance on more bottom-up processing is usually appropriate".

Unlike the earlier models of reading which were linear, later models tend to be interactive considering reading as a process of combining textual information with the information the reader brings to a text. Stanovich (1980) stated, "Interactive models assume that a pattern is synthesized based on information provided simultaneously from several knowledge sources" (Cited in Samuels and Kamil, 1988, p. 32). Based on these models, reading involves both lower-level automatic identification skills and higher-level interpretation skills operating interactively (Carrell, 1988c; Eskey and Grabe, 1988; Jonz, 1987; Samuels and Kamil, 1988). As Carrell (1988c, p. 101) informed us, schema-theory research has shown that "the most efficient processing of the text is interactive, a combination of top-down and bottom-up processing models leading to a modification of preexisting background knowledge and current predictions on the basis of information encountered in the text." Such a view takes into account "the dynamic process of reading in which the reader, text, task, process and the setting condition of the reading situation interact in an active and flexible manner" (Geva, 1992, p. 733).

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

In this view, the reading process is not simply a matter of extracting information from the text. Rather, it is one in which the reading activates a range of knowledge in the reader's mind that he or she uses, and that, in turn, may be refined and extended by the new information supplied by the text. Reading is thus viewed as a kind of dialog between the reader and the text. It is considered to be "part of a cycle of communication between writer and reader" (Marshall & Glock, 1978, p. 48). According to Riley (1985, pp. 71, 72), "Reading is not disembodied information retrieval ... but it is a communicative act, the transformation of text into discourse."

The process of pragmatic mapping--defined by Oller (1979, p. 33) as "the systematic correspondence between linguistic and extra linguistic context"—"is normally initiated by the bottom-up activation of schemata ... and is propelled ... by both the top-down organizational and expectational contribution of those activated schematic knowledge structures as well as continuing bottom-up activation and renewal of appropriate allied schemata" (Jonz, 1987, p. 411). As stated by Jonz (1987), "Meaning is prompted by textual features and constructed by the operation of personal, though socially constrained, knowledge structures" (p.410). Jonz (1987, p. 410) maintains:

Constructionists' explanations of language comprehension, assume that language users contribute actively to understanding, and that the context of comprehension is generated by the cognitive process of the comprehender. Meaning does not reside in the text but rather comes into being as a result of the interaction between text and language user Language users apply a limited cognitive resource to the proactive creation of a personal representation of the texts' meaning (p. 410).

McCarthy (1991) stated, "Making sense of a text is an act of interpretation that depends as much on what the reader brings to a text as what the author puts into it" (p. 27). Tierney, Bridge, and Cera (1978) accentuated:

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

The discourse processing operation of readers involves abstractive and constructive processes. Abstractive processing involves selective processing which seems promoted by the reader's attempt to 1) glean what might be considered relevant units from the text and 2) summarize the ideas in a manageable form in accordance with what can be handled by the memory system ... [During the constructive processing] readers process the input data, using information from the text in association with their background knowledge to construct a meaningful interpretation. (pp. 552, 554)

Reading, following Widdowson (1979), is "a reasoning ability whereby the reader creates meaning on the basis of textual clues" (p. 173). In the same manner, Shiro (1994) held, "A text takes shape (or different shapes) in the reader's mind during the reading process. A textual world is being built by combining textual information with inferences to form a coherent whole" (p. 167). She underlined that in this view, "inferences are understood as the information that is necessarily added to textual information in order to create new meaning" (p. 167). According to Johnston (1983), most of the models of reading built by the reader must be inferred since "text can never be fully explicit" (Carrell, 1991, pp. 160, 161). It, therefore, follows that the process of reading is affected by the knowledge and purpose of reader. As a result, "meanings derived are not precise but only approximations" (Widdowson, 1979, p. 173).

As Riley (1985, p. 66) put it, "reading is a highly idiosyncratic process since the knowledge we bring to bear on the text is the sum of previous experience." He maintained, "When a reader recreates discourse from a written text he performs the act of reading" (p. 72). The reader "constructs his own meaning in terms of his knowledge of the world and of the gaps in it which he is trying to fill in. The comprehension process is, therefore, closely linked to the reader's culture and personal background (Regent, 1985, p. 103). Gremmo (1985, p. 76) held that "the brain does not just record and compile; it controls the eye's movement by providing it with all sorts of non-visual information."

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

There are a number of different interactive models proposed, five of which will be mentioned here. According to Rumelhart's interactive-activation model, our higher order knowledge influences our analysis at a lower stage of analysis. This model suggest that "by means of separate knowledge sources [syntactic, semantic, lexical, and orthographic] and a message center which permits these sources to communicate and interact with each other, the higher order stages are able to influence the processing of lower level stages (Samuels & Kamil, 1988, pp. 29, 30). Grabe (1988, p. 61) contended:

The process of activation is essentially one in which individual features, letters, clusters, context, syntax, semantics, topic of discourse, background knowledge, etc, all excite (or activate) groups of lexical candidates for meaning, or comprehension selection. With more sources to rely on, only few of words pass to consciousness threshold, and this happens at a rapid rate so that its automaticity allows the reader to concentrate on comprehension.

The Stanovich's interactive compensatory model suggests that "deficit in any particular process will result in greater reliance on other knowledge sources, regardless of their level in the processing hierarchy"; in other words, it is assumed that "a process at any level can compensate for deficiencies at any other level" (qtd. In Samuels & Kamil, 1988, pp. 31, 32). Restoring to Slavonic's model, we may explain some student's over reliance on text of context. As Gravle (1988) relateed:

Certain students may overcompensate for a lack of relevant schemata by reading in a slow text-bound manner; other students may overcompensate by guessing [substituting the closet schemata]. In contrast, students who are not capable of rapid low- level processing may compensate by persevering word by word, or may overcompensate by guessing too often. (pp. 63, 64)

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Taylor, I and M Taylor's. cooperation model, "sets parallel processing strategies at a number of levels of text information," According to Taylors, " The processes of one track are fast and global attempt to find similarities between their input and familiar patterns. The processes of the other are slow and analytic and sort their input into elements in an attempt to find differences" (qtd. In Grabe, 1988, p. 62).

The fourth model, LaBerge and Samuels automatic-processing model was initially stresses the automatic recognition of words by fluent readers. This model was initially a serial bottom-up approach. Later on, feedback loops were added to it to make it interactive, allowing readers to move between higher and lower levels of processing as needed (Grabe, 1988, p. 62)

And the final model is Prefetti's verbal proficiency model whose core is the "processes of lexical access, proposition integration, and text model building" (qtd. In Grabe, 1988, p. 62).

Eskey (1988) argued that despite the emergence of interactive models, there is a strong top-down bias. He maintained that the role of the decoding aspect of the reading process should not be deemphasized and believed that "simple language decoding has a major role to play in the process—that good reading is more language structured than the guessing game metaphor seems to imply" (p. 94). He claimed:

For proper interpretation of the texts the latter skills [skills at higher cognitive level, i.e., top-down processing skills] are crucial, but such lower level skills as the rapid and accurate identification of lexical and grammatical forms are not merely obstacles to be cleared on the way to higher-level "guessing game" of the guesswork out of reading comprehension. (p.98)

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

A fluent reader is characterized by both skill at rapid, context-free word and phrase recognition and, of higher cognitive levels, the skillful use of appropriate comprehension strategies.

Geva (1992, p. 734) stated that according to van Dijk and Kintsch (1983), the process of reading comprehension involves:

... interpretation of phonemes, morphemes, and clauses. At the same time, clauses must be connected in sentences, coherent connection among sentences need to be established, and the reader needs to drive global macrostructure's to determine the topic of the passage. These interpretations, in turn, depend on general and episodic knowledge stored in memory. Thus memory must be searched and inferences have to be made to determine local and logical coherence. The reader needs also to activate knowledge of style, attitudes, goal, plans, and so on.

Geva (1992) later suggested that when these sub-processes of reading have not been automatized, parallel processing of all these becomes very cumbersome. Readers have to exert special effort on the preliminary stage of decoding lexical access and syntactic information; therefore, "they may not have enough resources for storage and for higher level text processing ...Furthermore, reader will be less efficient in utilizing knowledge controlling to global logical relations" (p. 735).

Eskey (1988, p. 94) said, "The automaticity by which readers identify lexical units and syntactical structures frees them to attend to comprehension." Consequently, due to recognition of the importance of these lower-level processes, Grabe (1991) stated that most current versions of interactive approaches to reading have taken a strong bottom-up orientation to the processing of lower-level linguistic structure.

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

And besides all, Grabe (1988) claimed that there is a third type of interaction to be considered in reading research: the interactive nature of the text that is being read. He said, "the linguistic elements of text combine interactively to create 'textuality' (i.e., what makes a text a text as opposed to collection of individual sentences)" (p. 64). He calls this interaction between linguistic forms to define textual functions, "textual interaction" (p. 65). Readers must be able to recognize these textual parameters as well in their process of reading.

Wolman (1991, p. 135) suggested that "to comprehend a text, the reader has to realize how the units of the text are connected." As Swaffar (1985) pointed out, L2 readers need to "identify the particular logic [of text] on the basis of intersentential relationships" (cited In Geva, 1992, p. 734). According to Jonz (1987), "features of text exert a strong influence on the meaning that language users, especially nonnative language users, derive from interacting with that text" (p. 410). Moreover, taking a constructionist's stance, he mentioned "language users employ text in comprehension as a set of guidelines to the active (re)creation of meaning," and adds, "It is this relationship between text, prior knowledge, and meaning that must be carefully studied and charted. Specifically, we must ascertain the exact role in comprehension and acquisition process" (p. 411). Therefore, the interactive model suggests the use of sensory, semantic, syntactic, and pragmatic information which provides information simultaneously, rather than serially.

The above mentioned interactive models have been elaborated clearly in a little bit different aspect as follows:

- a. McClelland and Rumelhart's (1981) interactive-activation model is based primarily on automatic and recognition research that the logon model of mental activation and information retrieval (Morton, 1969, 1979) presents. According to this model "individual letters, clusters, context, syntax, semantics, topics of discourse,

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

background knowledge, etc. all excite (or activate) groups of lexical candidates for meaning or comprehension selection" (Grabe; 1988a, p. 61).

b. Stanovich's (1980, 1984) interactive-compensatory model, based on word recognition processes, views reading as an "array of processes". The interactive-compensatory model, as Stanovich (1981, p. 262) states, "hypothesis that a pattern is synthesized based on information provided simultaneously from all knowledge sources and the process at any level can compensate for deficiencies at other level".

c. Taylor and Taylor's (1983) bilateral co-operation model combines features of Stanovich and Rumelhart models along with a range of neurolinguistic research. The bilateral co-operation model, as Taylor and Taylor (1983, p. 266) described:

postulates two tracks of processes that complement one another at each of several stages in understanding text. The processes of one track are fast and global and attempts to find similarities between their inputs and familiar patterns. The processes on the other hand are slow and analytic and sorts their inputs into elements in an attempt to find differences (Taylor & Taylor, 1983, p. 266).

d. LaBerge and Samuels' (1974) automatic processing model, initially a bottom-up processing approach (Samuels, 1977), in which the reader moves back and forth between lower and higher level of processing. As Grabe (1988a, p. 62) explained, "the automatic process of forms frees cognitive space for thinking about the meaning of what is being read. Thus, their (LeBerge and Samuels, 1974) claim is that fluent readers automatically recognize most words".

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

- e. Perfetti's (1985, 1986a, 1986b) verbal proficiency model argued that reading comprehension equates with processes of lexical access, proposition integration, and text model building, which are specific to reading.

2-5. Text processing

In addition to the importance of models in reading comprehension, text processing is also necessary for a better comprehension. Having developed a paradigm for structure of expository text, Mayer (1987) described several processes involved in reading comprehension as:

- Selecting relevant information from the passage
- Possessing relevant existing knowledge
- Building internal connections among the elements selected from the passage, and
- Building external connection between elements selected from the passage (1987, p. 448).

Van Dijk and Kintsch (1983) have proposed a representational scheme in which three distinct memory traces are distinguished. Each of these memory traces, which are listed below, results from a different source of information.

- a. Surface memory: Surface memory deals with the exact wording of a text, a product of highly automated lexical and syntactical processes.
- b. Text base memory: Text base memory corresponds to the content and structure of the text. It is the result of the process that derives the meaning of the text per se. Text base memory includes, as Weaver and Kintsch (1991, p. 238) mentioned, "micro-structure, macro-structure, and rhetorical schemata". It shows "the memory for text

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

itself and controls the reader's ability to produce the text in any form at a later date" (ibid).

c. Situation model: Situation model results from processes that integrate the information of the text with the reader's prior knowledge, and produces the most lasting traces in long-term memory. The situation model "corresponds to the equivalence class of all experiences (textual or otherwise) that convey the same situation" (Fletcher & Chrysler, 1990, pp. 175-176).

Weaver and Kintsch (1991) drew a line between text base memory and situation models in terms of their operation. They maintain that "when we are concerned with specific text and whether it is evaluated by summarization task, recognition or recall" text base memory matters. On the other hand, "when we are concerned with what the reader has learned from the text, how he or she will be able to use the textual information in new situation" (Weaver & Kintsch, 1991, p. 238) situation model is of importance.

The processing of text thus involves a triangular interaction between the writer, the creator of the text; the reader; and the text, the mediator that bridges the communication between reader and the writer. The reader reconstructs the text in her/his meaning making processes by means of activating his/her various types of prior knowledge such as conceptual or contextual knowledge, the knowledge about the structure and the organization of the text, and deriving information from the text focusing on the macro structure of the text, etc.

Not only reading but also comprehension is defined variously in the literature. In an attempt to distinguish between comprehension and interpretation, Urquhart (1987: 388-89) for example, quotes five definition of comprehension:

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

1. Comprehension is 'an information as the result of reading'...Comprehension is a response to the language system...The comprehension 'unit' thus consists of the text, the question, and the response (Bormuth, 1969).
2. According to Rumelhart (1984) 'readers are said to have understood the text when they are able to find a configuration of hypotheses (schemata) which offer a coherent account for the various aspects of the text'.
3. The reader's task in comprehending the text is said to consist of finding the organizational structure and modifying it for his own purpose (Calfee and Curley, 1984).
4. Baker and Brown (1984) describe nine activities crucial to good comprehension. Some of these are: establishing the purpose for reading; modifying reading rates and strategies in accordance with different purposes; identifying the important element of the passage; selecting appropriate standards for assessing one's level of comprehension.

According to Urquhart (1987, pp. 388-89) the value of Bormuth's definition of comprehension is 'his very explicit assertion that comprehension equals the ability to answer comprehension question'. Moreover 'meaning' according to this view is something fixed that resides in the text rather than something variable. However, as Urquhart put it, this definition can not be accepted in its entirety as a reader uses his or her schemata to create a representation of meaning from the text. Urquhart(1987) believed that the Rumelhart definition of comprehension is equivalent to his interpretation and the Calfee and Curley account of comprehension is inadequate as the comprehension resulting from scanning "does not seem to require much recognition of structure". The Baker and Brown's description of comprehension, according to Urquhart can distinguish between comprehension and interpretation.

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

The theory that describes a system of shaping, storing and retrieving different types of previous knowledge is known as "schema theory" which is briefly explained in the following section.

2-6. Schemata Theory

The idea of 'schemata' or 'schema', as it is used today, was first introduced by Bartlett (1932). According to Bartlett (1932), the term schema refers to "an active organization of reactions and past experience" (Cited in Anderson and Pearson, 1988, p. 39). He believed that individuals do not build the whole from the details, but they first get a general impression of the whole and then construct the possible details based on their impression (Anderson and Pearson, p. 40). Widdowson (1983, p. 54) defined schemata as "cognitive constructs or configuration of knowledge ... we place over events ... to bring them into alignment with familiar patterns of experience and belief. They therefore serve as devices for categorizing and arranging information so that it can be interpreted and retained." In the same way, Brown and Yule (1983, p. 247) consider schemata to be "higher-level complex (and even conventional and habitual) knowledge structures" (Van Dijk, 1981, 141), which function as 'ideational scaffolding' (Anderson, 1977) in the organization and interpretation of experience. They refer to schemata as "the organizational background knowledge which leads us to expect or predicts in our interpretation of discourse" (p. 248). According to Wilson and Anderson (1986) a schema is an abstract structure of knowledge. "It is structured in the sense that it indicates relation among constituent concepts. It is abstract in the sense that one schema has the potential to cover a number of texts that differ in particulars" (ibid, p. 33). The concepts, according to Wilson and Anderson (1986, p. 33), that "constitute a schema are said to provide slots that can be instantiated with specific information from the text." The requirement for comprehending a message that is the reader's ability to activate or construct a schema that provides a sensible account of the objects and the events in a discourse.

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Anderson and Pearson (1988) defined schemata as "an abstract knowledge structure" (p. 42) and maintain that in interpreting new information, schemata or "knowledge already stored in memory" is involved. They contend that by using the term comprehension, we actually mean the interaction between new information and old knowledge. "To say that one has comprehended a text is to say that he/she has found a mental 'home' for the information in the text, or else that he/she has modified an existing mental home in order to accommodate that new information" (ibid, p. 37). Carrell and Eisterhold (1988, p. 76) believed that "efficient comprehension requires the ability to relate the textual material to one's own knowledge." As notified by Tierney, Bridge and Cera (1979), "Memory for discourse is an active process of reconstruction in which the present knowledge system of the individual forms a scheme that interact with the new information in the text" (p. 553). According to Ausubel, in meaningful learning, "already-known general ideas 'subsume' or 'anchor' the new particular propositions found in texts" (in Anderson and Pearson, 1988, p. 41).

From the perspective of schemata theory, the principle determinant of the knowledge he or she already possess (Hudson, 1988, p. 185). This knowledge, contended Ackerman (1991, p. 135), function as the raw material for reader's inferencing processes. "He suggested that prior knowledge is not "value neutral" and it "motivates and situates the construction of a mental representation as much as it supplies an ideational network for inferencing processes" (p. 135).

As Marshal and Glock (1979) put it, "the idea that the memory of the reader controls, to a considerable extent, the way in which information is processed is called schema theory" (p. 50). They say that schema is described as "a loose network of information already in the mind of the reader that can affect comprehension" (p. 50). The more the reader already knows about a topic, the better the comprehension will be. Ernest Horn (1937) recognized, "[The author] does not really convey ideas to the reader; he merely stimulates him to reconstruct them out of his own experience" (p. 41). Carrell and Eisterholld (1983) held that schemata theory "only provides directions for readers as to

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

how they should receive or construct meaning from their own previously acquired knowledge" (p. 76). Widdowson (1984, p. 93) cited, "Neisser proposes a perceptual cycle whereby a schema directs the perceiver to explore reality by sampling the available information and modifying the original one."

According to McCarthy (1991), new knowledge can only be processed in relation to existing knowledge framework. He (p. 168) said, "The frameworks are not only knowledge about the world (e.g. about natural phenomena, about typical sequence of real life events and behavior), but also about text, how texts are typically structured and organized," thus enabling us to talk about two kinds of schemata: content and formal schemata, respectively. Put another way, content schemata refers to "background knowledge of the content area of the text," and formal schemata refers to "background knowledge of the formal *rhetorical organizational* structure of the text" (Carrell, 1988, p. 104). A reader's failure to activate the needed schemata may be either due to the lack of appropriate schemata as anticipated by the writer, or due to lack of enough cues in the text to be used in a bottom-up fashion to activate those schemata. One of the reasons for the former case is that "the schemata are specific to a given culture and are not part of a particular reader's background knowledge" (Carrell, 1988, p. 240). Steffenson and Joag-dev (1984) have shown that comprehension can be radically affected by the reader's cultural background (in Anderson & Urquhart, 1988). And the latter leads to the conclusion that there should at least be some language proficiency, a "language threshold" or "language ceiling", to be able to use the cues in the text to activate the relevant schemata.

According to schema theory, schemata, the organized knowledge, are accessed during reading. Wilson and Anderson (1986, p. 35) summarized the function of schemata as:

1. A schema provides ideational scaffolding. It embodies structural organization of the information it represents.

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

2. A schema enables inferential elaboration. ...the reader's schema provides basis for making inferences that go beyond the literally stated information to complete the meaning of the text, thus ensuring comprehension.
3. A schema allows orderly searches of memory. A schema has slots for certain types of information. Thus it can guide the reader to the kinds of information that need to be recalled.
4. A schema facilitates editing and summarizing. A schema contains criteria for the relative importance of different information. A reader can draw on these criteria in order to compute summaries that include significant propositions and omit trivial ones.
5. A schema permits inferential reconstruction. When there are gaps in memory for the text, the reader's schema - coupled with the specific text information that can be recalled – helps to generate hypotheses about the missing information.

To provide the reader with a more comprehensive account of schemata research methodology in second language reading comprehension area as well as the mechanism employed in this field of investigation. To this end the researcher found it most suitable to brief the reader on the content of an article by Patricia L. Carrell (1987) in which the author has presented her readers a comprehensive account of issues linked with research in reading proficiency, culture-specific content schemata and formal schemata, as well as any potential interaction between them. In the paper, the author (p.1) addresses the following major points: one type of schema, or background knowledge, a reader brings to a text is a content schema, which is knowledge relative to the content domain of the text. Another type is a formal schemata, or knowledge relative to the formal, rhetorical organizational structures of different types of texts. Carrell (1987, p.1) stated, in empirical tests of these two different types of schemata, it is fairly to separate out and to test for the effects of one type, while holding the effects of the other type constant. For example, in testing for the effects of content schemata, one keeps the formal rhetorical structure of a text constant, manipulates the content, and has

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

comparable groups of subjects process each different content. Any differences on the dependent measures (answers to literal or inferential questions, written or recall protocols, summaries, and so on) are then presumed to be due to the manipulation of content and reader's background knowledge of the content. She added: This type of research has in fact been typical in the field.

The seminal study of Steffensen, Joag-dev, and Anderson (1979) is a good example of this type of cross-cultural research on content schemata. In that study, two groups of subjects with different cultural heritages were investigated—a group of Asian Indians living in the United States and a group of Americans. Each subject was asked to read and recall two personal letters, both of which were constructed with similar rhetorical organization. However, the cultural content of two letters differed; one described a traditional Indian wedding, The other a traditional American wedding, It was assumed that all adult members of a society would have a well-developed system of background knowledge about the marriage customs of their own culture and a relative lack of knowledge about the marriage customs of more distant cultures. This is exactly what Steffen et al (1979) found. Both the Indian and American groups read the material dealing with their own cultural background faster and recalled more of the content. Furthermore, members of culture provided more appropriate cultural elaborations; nonmembers provided inappropriate cultural distortions, frequently outright intrusions from their own culture. In short, the study showed the clear and profound influence of cultural content schemata on reading comprehension (Carrell, 87, p.1).

Likewise, as Carrell (1987 , p. 2) goes on, one can test for the effects of formal schemata by keeping the content of a text constant, varying the rhetorical organization, and having comparable groups of subjects process each different rhetorical pattern. Again, one measure differences between the groups on some dependent measure(s) expected to be affected by the difference in comprehension due to the manipulation of form. The same types of dependent measures have been used in this type of schema research: scoring recall protocols or summaries for the number and types of

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

propositions or idea units they contain compared with the original text, or looking at the way different types of literal and inferential questions about the text are answered. At least two different studies of this type have been conducted in ESL reading, one with narrative text (Carrell, 1984b) and one with expository text (Carrell, 1984a).

Carrell (1984b, p.2) investigated the effects of a simple narrative formal schema on reading in ESL and found differences among ESL readers in the quantity and temporal sequence of their recall between standard and interleaved versions of simple stories. Quantity of recall was enhanced when the story's rhetorical organization conformed to a simple story schema—one well-structured episode followed by another. When stories violated the story schema, the temporal sequencing of readers' recall tended to reflect the story schematic order of presentation in the story. With expository prose, Carrell (1984a) investigated the effect of four different English rhetorical patterns on the reading recall of ESL readers of various native language background. Using text in which identical content information was structured in four different expository patterns, that study showed that the more tightly organized patterns of comparison, causation, and problem/ solution generally facilitated the recall of specific ideas from a text more than a more loosely organized pattern called collection of descriptions. There were, however, additional differences among the four native language groups and the four expository text types.

Clearly, prior research on content schemata suggests that, texts on content from the subject' cultural heritage, that is, texts with familiar content, should be easier to read and comprehend than texts on content from a distant, unfamiliar cultural heritage. Similarly, research on formal schemata clearly suggest that texts with familiar rhetorical organization should be easier to read and comprehend than texts with unfamiliar rhetorical organization. However, without research on combined, simultaneous effects of content and formal schemata, no specific predictions can be made about the separate or possibly interactive effects of these two types of schemata. The relative strengths of content and formal schemata in relation to each other are

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

unknown. While previous research leads to the prediction that reading a familiar content in a familiar rhetorical form should be relatively easy and that reading an unfamiliar content in an unfamiliar rhetorical form should be relatively difficult, no specific hypotheses follow from the previous research about reading a familiar content in an unfamiliar rhetorical form (Carrell, 19 , p. 3)

Another article by Ana Cristina Lahuerta Martinez (2002) in an empirical examination of EFL readers' use of rhetorical information investigated the use of text structure as a tool to facilitate and improve EFL students, comprehension of a text written in a foreign language. It explains the results of an experimental study carried out to analyze the relationship between use of the rhetorical organization that a text employs, on the one hand, and the comprehension and the reproduction of information of the text on the other. It was found that it is only when reproduction and conscious recognition coincide in the reader, that the structure has a positive effect on reading comprehension and reproduction of the information presented in a text. When the reader does not recognize the organization of the text (even if he reproduces it), this structure does not effect the reader's performance (p.1).

Martinez adds, we make a proposal for teaching reading comprehension in a non-native language based on the exploitation of text structure, making our readers aware of and capable of interpreting the rhetorical information a text presents. We state, our exploitation of text structure as a tool to improve reading comprehension is part of an approach to the teaching of reading comprehension, the ultimate objective of which is to make readers capable of an intentional processing based on the adequate and effective use of two types of knowledge depending on the reading situation they face: the first, knowledge of semantic relations, that is, how sentences may be joined by comparison, causality, etc., or how paragraphs may express two contrasting ideas, and the second knowledge of the way these relations are manifested in the text, in other words the lexical, syntactic resources the foreign language employs to express them. This processing implies the procedural capacity to draw on relevant knowledge sources

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

and select information from different levels (linguistic and nonlinguistic) in an adequate way (p.2).

Martinez (2002, p. 2) claimed, to learn a language means to learn words and sentences, and also the procedures to retrieve and process them. That is, the process of learning needs both declarative and procedural knowledge. In Martinez's paper the focus is on the kind of procedural knowledge that relates to comprehension: comprehension involves extracting the meaning in the light of all available linguistic cues in combination with the learner's general knowledge of the world. Martinez maintained, we distinguish between top-level and bottom-level comprehension to study which cues to meaning learners use. The top-level is constituted by knowledge system, that is, the schematic knowledge. Complementarily, the bottom-level is constituted by the language system, i.e. the informant's knowledge of the L2 at the various linguistic levels (systemic knowledge). Our approach to the use of structure is integrated within a reading model which takes both levels into account. It is a discourse semantic approach to reading (p.2).

Martinez (2002) goes on that, the general structure of this model is particularly derived from Widdowson's (1983) theory of language use, in which for the first time two traditions of research, schema theory and discourse analysis, are put together in an appropriate framework. According to this model, readers makes use of two types of knowledge in reading comprehension: systemic and schematic knowledge which correspond to the readers' linguistic and communicative competence respectively. And through procedures of interpretation, which are part of the readers' discourse competence in top-down/bottom-up directions, they relate their schematic knowledge (content and formal) to textual clues, actualizing in this way the text as discourse. The text is interpreted so that the linguistic elements have a communicative value in addition to linguistic meaning(p.2).

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Some types of schemata, that is the reader's prior knowledge of text structure, culture, world knowledge, and content have been widely researched in reading. The reader and text variables are important in reading comprehension. Martinez (p. 2) follows a type of analysis of discourse structure which looks into discourse structure from the point of view of reader, trying to detect in the surface structure of discourse the elements which allow the reader to interpret text. This view is presented by Winter (1977, 1982, 1992), Hoey (1979, 1983, 1991) and Jordan (1984, 1992). According to this view of structure from the interpreter's point of view, discourse is framed at a lower level into binary discourse relations, that is relations such as cause-effect, condition-consequence, etc., which are themselves part of the general level of organization (discourse macro-patterns). The rhetorical organization is manifested through resources in the language system. Linguistic resources have a schematic function because what they do is to prepare the reader for the recovery of discourse from the written text through interpretative procedures (ibid, p. 3).

In addition to schematic knowledge related to the local level of rhetorical organization of discourse structure, readers also possess formal schemata of a global. This relates to the global organization of the text, i.e. how the different elements of the communicative dynamics of the text make it hang together as a whole. According to this view, the rhetorical information is interpreted from the actual interplay between local and global schematic knowledge. This interpretation assumes the selection and integration of information in an intentional way: the reader will focus on a global formal schematic level, on the local formal schematic level, or on the systemic level depending on the reading situation (p.3).

Martinez believes research has shown how formal schematic knowledge is activated in reading comprehension. More specifically, when the readers reproduce the rhetorical organization of the text they recall more information from the passage and understand passage better. Carrell's (1984b) study is one of the few which centered specifically on the effect of text structure on ESL readers. She addressed the question of whether there

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

are any differences among non-native readers of English of varying native language and cultural background in their interaction with English expository texts of different rhetorical organization. She conducted an experiment to investigate the effects of these various different English rhetorical patterns on the reading recall of adult ESL students. The most interesting finding was that if ESL readers possess the appropriate formal schema against which to process the discourse type of the text, and, if they that formal schema to organize their recall protocols, more information is retrieved (p.3).

Block's (1986) study examined strategies used by second language readers and considers the use of text structure as a strategy. Block categorized strategies into two levels: general comprehension and local linguistic strategies. General strategies include comprehension-gathering and comprehension-monitoring. Recognition of text structure is included among general strategies. Local strategies deal with attempts to understand specific linguistic units (Martinez, p.2). This study showed how many L2 readers possess strategic resources to control their reading. However, only some of them are able to use those resources as an aid; most apply them sporadically and unsystematically. In this experiment, the readers who use background knowledge of textual organization improved their reading comprehension and recall (ibid. p. 3))

Carrell (1985) reported a control training study designed to answer the question of whether ESL reading can be facilitated by teaching text structure explicitly. The training introduces the reader into the use of organization as a key for understanding. Students are given an explanation of description; causation problem/solution and comparison types of rhetorical organization and signals that mark each type to show readers how to use the corresponding rhetorical organization to organize their writing. The results indicated that training in rhetorical organization of expository texts significantly increased the amount of information that 25 intermediate-level ESL students could recall. The same conclusion was drawn by Chou Hare, Robinowitz and Schieble (1989) and Berry, Scheffler and Goldman (1993) from studies which focused

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

on teaching structure as an aid for reading performance (comprehension and recall of information) (Martinez, p. 3)

Sunyoung Shin (2002) in an article described two other important factors in reading comprehension. In this article (p. 1) states, although the processes of reading are often too dynamic and varied for different readers on different texts to be investigated, it is generally accepted that the interaction between readers and text variables is key to understanding the reading process. As a result, it has become common practice to divide reading-related research into two separate factors: The reader and the text (Alderson, 2000).

2-7.1. Reader variables and reading comprehension

Sunyoung Shin (2002) claimed, when it comes to reader variables, the state of the reader's knowledge, broadly speaking, constitutes one significant reader variable, as does the reader's motivation to read. It is clear that the nature of the knowledge that readers bring to the reading process will affect the way they process and understand text. The development of schema theory has attempted to determine the degree to which readers' knowledge affects what they understand. Schemata are seen as interlocking mental structures representing readers' knowledge (Anderson, 2000). When readers process a text, they integrate the new information from the text into their schemata. Schemata are often divided into formal schemata and content schemata. The former refers to knowledge of the language and linguistic conventions, including the organization of the text. The latter pertains to knowledge of the world, including the subject matter of the text (Shin, p. 2).

In second language reading research, it has been presupposed that the learners must acquire linguistic knowledge before they can read. In particular, lexical knowledge of the text has been seen as essential for second language readers to process texts. According to Cooper (1984), without sufficient lexical knowledge, L2 readers showed

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

substantial inability to use linguistic cues in the large context in order to deduce meaning and to recognize lexical relationship and meaning relationships between sentences (Shin, p. 2).

In addition to L2 linguistic knowledge, the transfer of L1 reading ability has also been investigated. Bernhardt and Kamil (1995) claimed that L1 reading ability was a strong predictor of L2 ability based on their findings that L1 reading ability accounted for 20% of the variability in test taker's reading scores. However, they argue that L2 linguistic knowledge was a consistently more powerful predictor, accounting for more than 30% of the variance (Shin, p. 2).

With regard to the effects of the reader's content schemata on reading ability, Rumelhart (1985) showed that readers need knowledge about the content of the passage in order to be able to understand it. In other words, L2 readers are able to integrate new information with their previous knowledge related to it, but they find it difficult to integrate new information with non-existent information in processing texts (Shin, p. 2).

As it is elaborated in schemata theory, taking into account some variables of the expected readers of the text, e.g. readers' prior knowledge of the content, of the culture, etc., and employing a rhetorical organization for composing the text, seem to be well-established practices for writers. Readers, in turn, are also expected to activate a set of variables such as their previously acquired knowledge on the topic at issue, on the text structure, etc., to integrate the meaning units of the text both locally and globally, and to draw inferences in order to understand and interpret the text and capture the writer's intention. This interaction implies that the writer's real intention may be misunderstood unless the readers bring into the text the relevant variables that the writer took into account in the process of creating the text.

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Reading theorists in first language (Newkirk, 1989; Smith, 1971) and in second or foreign language (Barnett, 1989; Carrell, Devine and Eskey, 1988; Grab, 1991; Wallace, 1988) highlighted the influence of various types of readers' prior knowledge in constructing meaning from the text. These studies demonstrated that readers, the same as writers who create texts, construct meaning from the text by employing their previously acquired knowledge such as content knowledge, cultured knowledge, world knowledge, etc. Opinions of researchers on the effect of these variables on reading comprehension, however, vary. Steffensen and Joag Dev (1984), for example, maintained that what readers understand from the text depend on the readers and their prior knowledge rather than on the text. Carrell and Eisterhold (1983, p. 73) also believed that "much of the meaning understood from the text is really not actually in the text, *per se*, but in the reader, in the background or schematic knowledge of the reader". On the other hand, Eskey (1988) believed some understanding of the text can take place without activating the reader's background knowledge.

According to Roller (1990), the studies which were mainly carried out in the first language, have demonstrated the decisive effect of readers' prior knowledge on their meaning making process while failing to respond to the question of "how readers acquire the world knowledge they bring to the text..., and how they acquire new knowledge from the text" (1990: 83). Research on the relationship between the reader variable, i.e. having topic knowledge, and text comprehension in the foreign language has also yielded the same results. Based on their investigation of the influence of academic disciplines on the performance of readers on reading comprehension tests, Alderson and Urquhart (1988, p. 182) concluded that "academic background can have an effect on reading comprehension" of non-native speakers of English.

Meyer (1975), based on a number of empirical studies (Meyer and Freedle 1984, 1980), claimed that ideas are more easily remembered when presented in tightly-organized texts because of the close link between ideas. Her claim has been supported by other researchers (e.g., Carrell 1984; Goh 1990; McGee 1982, cited in Kobayashi, p. 3).

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Johnson (1981) argued that familiarity with a topic and general background knowledge of a theme may be more important than vocabulary knowledge and might allow the reader to construct “plausible meaning” for unfamiliar vocabulary. The results of this study did not support a high correlation between vocabulary knowledge and real comprehension but rather demonstrated that “familiarity with a foreign-culture-related topic obtained through experience is effective for reading comprehension of a passage on that topic” ... Exposure to meanings difficult vocabulary words in the passage did not affect the comprehension of ESL reader.”

Mann and Thompson (1988, p. 260) argued that “recognition of rhetorical relation of a text which is The basis of coherence is essential to understanding the text.” Hudson (1991, p. 83) believed that "simultaneous application of elements such as content and purpose along with knowledge of grammar, content, vocabulary, discourse convention, graphing-knowledge and metacognitive awareness” are involved in constructing an appropriate meaning in the text. Mitchell (1987, p. 607) also maintained that “readers must do more than identifying the individual words in the sentence. They must compute all the structural relationship between them” in order to comprehend the text.

2.7-2. Text structure and reading comprehension

Research has indicated that understanding how a passage is structured is an important factor in reading comprehension (Bartlett, 1987; Mandler and Johnson, 1977; Meyer, 1979, 1982). More specifically, it has been clearly established that readers who are able to identify top-level structure ("the rhetorical relationship that can interrelate the greatest amount of text" [Meyer, 1985, p. 269]) as well as paragraph-level relationships of a passage are better able to understand than are those readers who remember only a collection of details. An area of structure comprehension that has remained relatively unexplored, however, is that of microstructure—that aspect of text structure that refers to the author's progression from given to new information. Included in the structure at this level is the use of certain linguistic cues that provide the reader with the

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

information about what author expects the reader to be holding in memory (Demel, 1990, p. 1).

Shin in an article (2002, p. 3) contended, the other side of the reader-text interaction is the text itself. In text variables, many aspects of the text might facilitate or make the reading process difficult. Although the language of the text is known to be the major variable, there are other factors ranging from aspects of the text content, to text types, text organization, and sentence structures. Nevertheless, research has shown that lexical and syntactic knowledge in L2 are the strongest predictors in L2 reading performance among other factors (Bernhardt and Kamil, 1995; Cooper, 1984). However, when the linguistic variables, for example, lexis and sentence structures, are controlled in a reading test, such variables as reader's sub-skills and text types are more likely to influence their reading performance (Shin, 2002, p. 3).

Text structure has been studied with reference to all sorts of text including expository and narrative texts. Broadly speaking, the former, consisting of textbooks, scientific and technical writing, training manuals, etc., aims at communicating various pieces of information and in the literal mode; while the latter, including writing such as story, novel, etc., primarily tries to entertain their readers and in the metaphoric mode.

Different approaches have been used to clarify the text structure of these two types of writing. The structure of narratives as weaver and Kintsch (1991, p. 238) put "can be described in terms of episodes of the form *setting – complication – resolution*, or alternatively in terms of story grammar, or causal event chains, and so on". But the structures of expository text typically "are described in terms of such schemata as classification, illustration, comparison and contrast and procedural" (ibid.).

There is a long tradition research in to the differences between expository and narrative texts. Generally, it has been suggested that expository texts are harder to process than narrative texts, perhaps because of the greater variety of relationships among text units,

or possibly due to greater variety of content types (Alderson, 2000). A large number of empirical studies has demonstrated that narratives typically have a hierarchical structure, that readers are sensitive to such structure, and when the structure is used to guide comprehension and recall, both are facilitated (Glenn, 1978; Mandler, 1978; Carrell, 1985). In addition, narrative texts are more likely to induce visualization in the reader as part of the reading process than the expository texts (Dennis, 1982, qtd in Shin, p. 6).

2.8. Studying Features of Expository Text

Three aspects of expository texts--that is rhetoric, teaching of expository text structure, and cognitive aspect of expository text-- have been widely investigated, but they have a different historical research background. Rhetorical features and expository text structure instruction have been investigated for a long time. Research about rhetorical features has a long history, for rhetoric has been "a formal academic discipline since antiquity" (Weaver and Kintsch, 1991, p.230). Investigating expository text structure instruction correspond to research on study skills. Pearson and Fielding (1991: 827), referring to Anderson and Armbruster (1984), say all of the work on the effects of underlining, outlining, note taking, or summary instructions is an attempt to sensitize students to the usefulness of focusing on, or representing the author's arguments as an aid to comprehending, learning and remembering (Perfetti, 1985; Van Dijk and Kintsch, 1983).

Some studies in the past three decades have also been devoted to exploring the various dimensions of expository text. Crothers (1979) and Frederikson (1975, 1977) analyzed text concentrating on the logical relation existing between text units. Meyer (1975, 1985) emphasized hierarchical semantic relations between idea units of the text. Halliday and Hassan (1976) developed a classification system for explicit logical relations. Kintsch and van Dijk (1978) developed an argument repetition approach to show the relationship that arise out of repetition of concepts in a text, and distinguished micro and macro structure of a text in order to explain the understanding of a text.

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Mann and Thompson (1988) developed an approach for examining the coherence of the text on the hierarchical rhetorical relations that exist between units of a text.

In line with the studies that examined the effect of reader related variables on understanding the text content, some other investigations were carried out to explore the relationship between text structure variables and comprehension of the text content. Some researchers (Kintsch, Mandel and Kozminsky, 1977; Kintsch and Yarbrough, 1982) focused on scramble sentences and paragraphs and investigated the comprehension of disrupted ideas in the rearranged sentences or paragraphs. Others (Kieras, 1985; Meyer, 1975; Spyridakis and Standal, 1987) manipulated the text they used in their study by re-writing a text retaining or changing the structure of the original text. Another group of researchers (Rinehart, Stahl and Erikson, 1986; Winograd, 1984; Carrell, 1992) investigated text structure awareness. And finally other researchers (Kieras, 1985; Meyer, 1975; Meyer 7 Freedle, 1984, Carrell, 1984, 1985) compared the structure of text with the structure of readers' performance. These studies came up with mixed results. But, in general, these studies, as Roller (1990, p. 2) said 'found that the position of super-ordinate or subordinate information in the text hierarchy affects reader's performance on a range of dependent measures.'

Researchers on text structure propose that sensitivity to text structure is an influential component in text comprehension. This motivated some language practitioners to concentrate on teaching something about the text structures and how they can be used to organize text information in teaching reading or study skills. Pearson and Fielding (1991: 832) emphasized the role of text structure in teaching reading:

In general, we have found incredibly positive support for just about any approach to text structure instruction for expository text. It appears that any sort of systematic attention to clues that reveal how authors attempt to relate ideas to

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

one another or any sort of systematic attempt to impose structure upon a text, especially in some sort of visual representation of the relationships among key ideas, facilitates comprehension as well as both short-term and long-term memory for the text.

Two sets of findings, as Pearson and Fielding (1991: 827) put it, fuelled the teaching of text structure as an aid to comprehension. First, students familiar with text structure remember more of the text than those who did not (Barlett, 1978; McGee, 1982). Second, more good readers than poor readers followed the writer's structure in their attempts to recall the text information (Taylor, 1980).

Finally, as Widdowson (1984) mentioned, whereas the writer's task is to use linguistic and communicative conversations to convey their own propositions, reader's task is to derive the intended meaning from the text and reconstitute the writer's intentions.

2.9. Recall protocols and reading comprehension

Some researchers wanted to know what it is that people actually do in order to understand written or spoken language. To begin to answer this question, a means of data collection new to the study of reading was evolved. Instead of collecting test scores, the researchers developed more open ended tasks that had proved successful in previous learning research. The two most frequently used of these were recognition and recall. In both cases, a subject would be given a passage to read (or listen to) .Then the subject would either select sentences or words he recognized as being in the passage(recognition) or would attempt to produce the passage in his or her own words (recall), Recall, in particular, proved immensely valuable because both the individual differences and the common threads in what was recalled were available to the researcher. This knowledge- telling model would suggest that what goes on mentally in the writer while composing should bear a close resemblance to what appears on the

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

page. The knowledge-transforming model, however, would suggest that among more mature writers there should be a great deal of activity revealed in thinking-aloud protocols that is not directly represented in the text. Recall protocols are also referred to as an indirect means of testing hypothesis about mental representation of text. The assumption is that, in trying to recall things about their texts, writers make use of whatever stored knowledge is connected with what they are trying to recall. It is expected that mature writers use complex routes to retrieving text information, passing through representations of a variety of kinds, where as immature writers should make use of a smaller variety of representations and depend more on direct recall of whatever is asked. Thus, by studying recall for information presented in a passage. "one is not just studying the process of comprehension for written material. One is also studying the process of thinking, or at least of that part of thinking that seems to be linguistically encoded "(Mershall and Glock, 1979, p. 13).

2.10. Effects of text structure awareness on recall

Another line of research concerning the validity of recall protocols as a means of assessing information structure is the one carried out by Carrell (1992) on text structure and reading recall. That research has shown significant effects on EFI ESL reading of differences in both narrative and expository rhetorical patterns (Carrell. 1984a, 1984b, 1985). Research in reading in English as a native language has shown not only these same effects of differences in rhetorical patterns (Meyer, 1975, 1977, 1979) but has also shown that students awareness of structural patterns, especially in expository writing, also affects reading. Differences in awareness of structural patterns have correlated with differences in the type and amount of information recalled after reading expository texts (Taylor, 1980; McGee, 1982). Researches in ESI/EFL reading carried out by Carrell (1992) have explicitly investigated the same types of relationships between awareness and recall performance on different types of expository text structures. Quantitatively, those subjects who used the structure of the original passages to organize their written recalls recalled significantly more total ideas than did those who did not. There were no such differences for the recognition measure of awareness; subjects who recognized the structure of the original passages did not recall

significantly more total ideas than did those who did not so, it can be concluded that awareness and recall are not separate phenomena. It is also to be stated that those readers who possess a special kind of awareness of different patterns used by authors to organize expository texts would be more likely to understand and remember well-structured texts and "they recall more ideas in total number of ideas and also recall more of the main ideas and major ideas of the text."(Carrell , 1992, p. 15)

2.11. The recall protocol procedure in L2 reading assessment

In a study of recall, Anderson (1984) stated that students recall significantly more material when their schemata have been activated. He also reported that interest is a much more important factor affecting recall than readability. One surprising finding in this study was that recall is not correlated with the amount of time spent on the reading, which implies that poor performance is related to the effectiveness of the reading processes, not time consideration. His interpretation of this finding is that reading involves deep semantic processing, which is not dependent on the amount of time spent. He concluded that the reader's background knowledge is the most significant factor affecting recall. (qtd. in Chastain, 1978, p.233).

Peter J. Heinz in an article (2004, p. 1) stated, second language reading comprehension assessment has long relied upon classical quantitative, product-oriented measurement techniques (i.e., multiple-choice and cloze) in both research and classroom assessment. As Bernhardt (1991) clearly demonstrated, these traditionally employed assessment methods are unable to capture the complex processes that take place between learner and the text. However, in order to remedy this problem, a new and welcome trend in reading comprehension assessment emerged that looked "more carefully at the authenticity of the assessment tasks and their alignment with current research, theory and instructional practices" (Valencia, 1990: 60). "The immediate free recall protocol", unlike the multiple choice or cloze tests, is a truly integrative authentic-task measure, firmly grounded on a constructivist model of reading comprehension (p.1). Significant

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

attention in the second language reading comprehension assessment literature revolves around the development of a dynamic, learner-based, constructivist model of reading comprehension that demands new and equally dynamic paradigms of assessment (Alderson, 2000; Bernhardt and DeVille, 1991; Maarof, 1998).

Operating under a learner-based theory of reading comprehension, Bernhardt (1991) found that "if a test is to adequately assess L2 reading ability it must acknowledge the status of the reader's knowledge base," and "a successful assessment mechanism must be integrative in nature" (p. 193). Heinz stated:

As a research-based, appropriate and suitable alternative, the recall protocol procedure is seen as a highly valid and effective L2 reading comprehension assessment measure that provides both qualitative and quantitative information (Berkemeyer, 1989;, 1991;; Lee, 1986, cited in Heinz, p. 2).

According to Berkemeyer (1989: 131):

It does not allow students to guess their way through the text...nor does it influence students' understanding of the text. In short, the immediate recall protocol demands that the reader comprehend the text well enough to be able to recall it in a coherent and logical manner....This procedure allows misunderstandings and gaps in comprehension to surface; a feature that other methods of evaluation cannot offer.

Bernhardt and others (e.g., Berkemeyer, 1991;; Lee, 1986, Maarof, 1988) have long championed the use of immediate, free-response reading recall protocol as a particularly efficacious measure of a learner-based L2 reading comprehension paradigm. That paradigm promotes a multifaceted reading comprehension research and assessment approach combining quantitative and qualitative methods in order to arrive at a more complete picture of the comprehension process. Clearly, the recall protocol

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

procedure can be an important part of that multifaceted approach. As Brisbois (1992: 168) noted:

....testing methods, such as the recall protocol procedure, need to gain wider acceptance as a measure of reading comprehension. Not only in the recall protocol more sensitive than discrete-point tests, but its sensitivity becomes more pronounced as reading proficiency increases.

Recall test is not hampered by possible inference from test items and is more likely to focus on the communication between text and reader. The assumption is that recall indicates something about the reader's assimilation and reconstruction of text information and therefore reflects comprehension (Gambrel, Pfeiffer and Wilson, 1985, qtd. In Sharp, p. 6).

In this connection, Carrell (1984b) investigated the effects of simple narrative formal schema on reading in ESL and found differences among ESL readers in the quantity and temporal sequence of their recall between standard and interleaved version of simple stories. Quantity of recall was enhanced when the story's rhetorical organization conformed to a simple story schema—one well-organized episode followed by another. When stories violated the story schema, the temporal sequencing of the readers' recall tended to reflect the story's schematic order rather than the temporal order of presentation in the story (p.2). Carrell's work was reduplicated by Goh (1990) and Talbol and Allan (1991) using exactly the same texts. For all these investigations the rhetorical pattern of the text was found to have an effect on reading comprehension as measured by recall (Sharp, p. 2).

With expository prose, Carrell (1984a) has shown the effects of four different English rhetorical patterns on the reading recall of ESL readers of varied native language

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

backgrounds. Using texts in which identical content information was structured in four different expository patterns, that study showed that the more tightly organized patterns of comparison, causation, and problem/solution generally facilitated the recall of specific ideas from a text more than a more loosely organized pattern called collection of descriptions. There were, however, additional differences among the four native language groups and the four expository text types (Carrell, p. 2).

Kintsch and Greene (1978), argued that simple structural story grammars typical of stories of European background may not be typical of stories of other cultural origins, reported differences in comprehension by American college students of text of European origin (e.g., Grimm's fairy tales) and text of American Indian origin (e.g., Apache Indian tales). They concluded from their result that the subjects' prior familiarity with the European-based rhetorical organization and their lack of familiarity with the rhetorical organization of the American Indian tales—that is, their formal schemata—was the cause of the American students' better comprehension of European texts. Some studies have been conducted on the effects of text structure on reader performance (Carrell, 1984, p. 2). The results of these studies showed that certain more highly structured English rhetorical patterns were more facilitative of meaningful recall for non-native readers. In general, these studies indicate an interaction between a reader's prior knowledge of processing strategies for text structure and the rhetorical organization of the text.

Recent research on text has provided evidence of the relationship between coherence and comprehensibility of a text. The concept of coherence has been to describe the extent to which the sequencing of ideas in a text makes sense and the extent to which the language used to present those ideas makes the nature of the ideas and their relationship apparent. Studies that present readers with more or less coherent versions of a text have shown that the more coherent versions yield better comprehension (Mckewn, Beck, Sinatra and Lexterman, 1992). Carrell (1985) reported a controlled training study designed to see if ESL reading can be facilitated by teaching text

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

structure explicitly. The training introduces the reader into the use of organization as a key for understanding. Students were given an explanation of description; causation; problem/ solution and comparison types of rhetorical organization and the signals that mark each type to show readers how to use the corresponding rhetorical organization to organize their writing. The results indicated that training in rhetorical organization of expository texts significantly increased the amount of information that twenty five intermediate-level ESL students could recall. The same conclusion was drawn by Chou Hare, Rabinowitz and Schieble (1989) from studies which focused teaching structure as an aid for reading performance (comprehension and recall of information).

Carrell (1992) investigated the relationship between awareness of text structure and recall performance with several types of text structure: comparison/contrast and collection of descriptions. Recall protocols were categorized as top-, high-, mid-and low- level. She also determined whether or not each recall protocol reflected the text structure of the original passage. Subjects were also asked to identify the type of text structure each of the passages. There was no significance difference between the quantity of idea units recalled for the two text types, but subjects did recall significantly more top-level idea units from the comparison/contrast passage. So, for the most part, text type did not affect recall. Awareness of text structure, however, affected both quantity and quality of recall. Those subjects who used the same type of structure as the original passage in their recall protocols recalled significantly more idea units (particularly top- and high level idea units) than those who did not organize their recalls in this way; those who only recognized the text structure and did not use it themselves recalled significantly less. Thus the strategy of using text structure does indeed enhance recall.

Carrell (1984) noted that knowledge of how texts are organized function like other schemata. She referred to these as formal schemata and conducted a series of studies to exact their effect on L2 reading comprehension. Research already done with L1 readers (Myer, Brandt and Bluth, for example) demonstrated that certain types of text were

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

processed differently than others. Carrell (1984) reported on the effect of different types of texts on reading comprehension of intermediate level ESL learners who were speakers of Spanish, Arabic, and Oriental languages. This study used four versions of a passage written in four different types of rhetorical organization: collection of descriptions, causation, problem/solution, and comparison. Results indicated that, except for the Arabic speakers, more tightly organized texts (causation, problem/solution and comparison) lend themselves to recall more readily than a more loosely organized text. Arabic speakers had lowest overall scores; however their recall of the collection of descriptions type of discourse was equal to their recall of problem/solution type, which was possibly due to the proffered rhetorical pattern of Arabic (p.464).

Leon and Carretero (1995, p. 204) noted the importance of text structure in "helping readers to differentiate between important and unimportant information as well as in the organization and recall of information".

2.12. Conclusion

According to what briefly covered about rhetorical organization, reading comprehension, and recall of information, it was materialized that to comprehend the writer's message in a text, the minimal requirement is that readers need some of the reading skills that the educationists enumerated. Readers, as the cognitivists point out, also need to be able to reconstruct a mental representation of the text, as well as the lexical, syntactic and semantic relations between elements of the text and propositional and rhetorical features of the text. Furthermore, it is only by activating the appropriate schemata that the readers will be able to interact with the text and discern the writer's intention. The investigation of the relationship of world knowledge, topic knowledge, and text structure to reading comprehension demonstrates the influential impact of these variables on reader-writer interaction and ultimately, text comprehension. Without these knowledge sources, the reader is unable to discern the writer's intention in relation to a particular text.

CHAPTER THREE

METHOD

3.1. Introduction

I describe the design of the research here. This section will specifically describe the participants of the study, the instruments used for data collection, the procedures for administration of the instruments, method of the data analysis, and the place of test administration. In order to assess if rhetorical organization affects comprehension and recall, the rhetorical patterns have to be isolated from other influences on comprehension. For this experiment, the researcher compared recall of two types of texts, that is, descriptive and causative of the same version and comprehension of some passages for control and experimental group. The researcher randomly chose two groups including an experimental and a control group. Each group consisted of 120 participants. Both groups received a proficiency test (PET) to select homogenous subjects. Then they received two pretests (a comprehension and a recall). The experimental group received at least two weeks of instruction, and the control group received no instruction. Finally, the researcher gave the same two pretests to both

CHAPTER THREE: METHOD

groups (EG and CG) and compared the results of the post tests of two groups to find out the possible impact of rhetorical explicit instruction on reading comprehension and recall of information. In fact, the two groups were compared according to their performance (comprehension and recall) in two organizational texts of recall and comprehension passages. Thus, the schematic representation for the design of this study after proficiency test is as follows:

		Explicit Instruction	Post-Test
Experimental Group(EG)	+	+	+
Control Group (CG)	+	-	+

3.2. Participants

The population from which the participants of the present study have been drawn includes sophomore students majoring in English language at Azad university of Malayer who were taking their third course of reading comprehension. They were preliminary selected at random from a pool of approximately 240 potential candidates. The researcher concerned to choose 240 homogenous students who were as equivalent as possible in terms of their previous exposure to EFL and on the part of their general language proficiency. These 240 homogenous participants have been chosen via language proficiency test that was extracted from PET. This test was made of vocabulary, grammar and reading comprehension. At the time of study the participants had been studying English for at least two years at university and four years before entering the university. They were randomly divided into two groups of 120 students. Then, they were randomly assigned to one control group and one experimental group. The result of proficiency test showed that two groups (EG and CG) were homogeneous on the part of their mean scores and standard deviation as follows:

Table 3.1 Group Statistics

	Subject Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Proficiency Test	Control Group	120	62.7000	12.58691	1.14902
	Experimental Group	120	61.5000	10.80383	.98625

3.3. Instruments

The materials used in the study consisted of five expository passages in the same level of difficulty. The passages were selected from TBRT-GM module which included true-false, sentence-completion, outlining, Writer's-View Elicitation and skimming forms. The passages for recall were typical of reading materials generally found in Carrell's experiment of rhetorical organization. In order to control the structure and content of the information while investigating the effects of discourse type, two versions of a single passage were selected for recall. The text was "the loss of body water" taken from Carrell (1984a). The researcher did not present the topic of the text to the participants because the effect of text structure varies depending on the extent of readers' knowledge of the topic of the text. Each version contained identical content information. Both texts had clear organizational patterns. The texts were written according to two general semantic relations between propositions: A collection of description and causation (they are in appendix B, p.....). The measuring instrument used in this study consisted of three phases: a proficiency test, a test of comprehension, and an intermediate recall test (reproduction of information test) as pretests and two post tests of recall and reading comprehension. Both groups (EG and CG) were given the same kind of recall texts and reading comprehension passages in the form of causative and descriptive as pretest and post-test.

In order to make the experimental group familiar with the concept of rhetorical organization and organizational patterns used in the texts, two units (eight and ten) of the book of advanced writing (1383) which had to do with descriptive and causative patterns were taught in the classroom. These units were instructed after pretest of recall and reading comprehension. There were some descriptive and causative patterns in these two units (eight and ten) which were analyzed and clarified in the classroom. Moreover, the descriptive and causative rhetorical patterns of a few articles such as Carrell (1987), Sharp (2002), and Martinez (2002) were delivered and analyzed in the classroom.

3.4. Procedures

The experimental design involves the use of an experimental group and a control group. The 240 participants who in two groups (EG and CG) participated in the experiment. Each group consisted of 120 subjects who were randomly chosen. Both groups received a proficiency test of PET to choose homogenous subjects on the part of their mean scores, two pretests (a comprehension and a recall) and two posttests the same as pretests. The comprehension tests were in the form of true-false, sentence-completion, outlining, Writer's-View Elicitation and skimming questions. The passages for recall were typical of reading materials generally found in Carrell's experiment of rhetorical organization. In the pretests phase, all the participants were tested in their classroom in a task which took approximately one hour in two separate sessions. Students were instructed to read for content, with the expectation that their comprehension and their remembering would be tested. They were told to read the texts they were given in the order in which they were stapled together, taking as much time as they needed to understand and remember the texts. They were told that they would be asked to write what they could remember of the texts of recall immediately, and to answer the reading comprehension questions. They were not allowed to make any written notes. The texts of recall were collected from them individually as they finished reading. Although reading time was individually controlled by each subject, as a group they took approximately 15 to 20 minutes to read each text. After the texts were collected, regular classroom procedures of recalling started without referring back to the contents of the texts. In eliciting their recall, participants were given recall booklets consisting of two stapled sheets of paper. At the top of each page was the number of each text intended as a recall cue. Subjects were asked to write their recall of each text, writing as much as idea units and as exactly as they could remember of each text. They were told to write as well as they could, but not to be overly concerned with their writing. We emphasized that we were interested in how well they understood and remembered the texts as they read them, not in how well they could write them down. As with reading time, writing time was subject-controlled. They were asked to write a recall of each text in English, paying attention to the semantic content as well as the order of propositions in each text.

CHAPTER THREE: METHOD

However, as a group, they spent approximately 20 to 30 minutes writing their recalls of the two texts. In the second phase, the EG received two weeks of explicit instruction of rhetorical organization and the CG received no instruction. In order to make the experimental group familiar with the concept of rhetorical organization and organizational patterns used in the texts, two units (eight and ten) of the book of advanced writing (1383) which had to do with descriptive and causative patterns were taught in the classroom. There were some descriptive and causative patterns in these two units (eight and ten) which were analyzed and clarified in the classroom. Moreover, the descriptive and causative rhetorical patterns of a few articles such as Carrell (1987), Sharp (2002), and Martinez (2002) were delivered and analyzed in the classroom.

Finally, both groups (EG and CG) received two post-tests the same as pretests. Then, the scores which obtained from pretests and post tests compared in terms of their means to see the effect of rhetorical organization instruction on recall and reading comprehension and compared the effect of rhetorical organization instruction with language proficiency as predictors on reading comprehension and recall of information .The researcher performed t-test, paired-samples t-test and a two-way ANOVA on the results of both post-tests. Therefore, each participant was randomly assigned to two texts for recall. In this way, each text was read by 240 participants. The independent variables were the presence of rhetorical organization and language proficiency. The dependent variables were the participants' comprehension of passages and recall of causative, descriptive texts. The participants were given the texts; they read the text at their own individual reading rates to find out what it said about the topic. An immediate written recall was then requested. The subjects were asked to write down everything they could remember from the text, using their own words. They were asked to only write in complete sentences and not just to list isolated words or ideas. They were to try to show in their own writing how the ideas from the text were related to each other. Later on, the participants were asked to answer the questions of reading comprehension after reading the texts of recall. The identical information in two text versions was reduced to a total of 21 idea units—based on Carrell (1984). Each recall was scored for presence or absence of 21 identical units. The researcher examined the overall rhetorical organization of the recall and classified it as either meeting the definition of the two

CHAPTER THREE: METHOD

original text types (collection of descriptions and causation) or not. The requirement of a collection of description type was a group of descriptions about a topic, where the descriptions were collectively organized. Recalls were classified as causation if the structure consisted of an antecedent and a result. In order to score the result of the comprehension test, the researcher scored each recall in terms of whether it showed the reader had understood the passage or not, using the following scale to measure the overall comprehension of the passage.

0 point: The subject does not understand the passage

.5point: The subject understands the passage in general. He/She, however, does not understand the whole passage

1 points: perfect comprehension of the passage

Recall protocols of the subjects were scored by making use of a loose criterion of recall. According to this criterion EFL readers would not be penalized for their vocabulary and grammatical shortcomings. Sentences in each protocol were matched with sentences in the original text that conveyed the same idea. For each subject, each sentence in the original text was then assigned one point. All sentences in the text that were not assigned one point were then assigned 0 point. No points were also assigned in cases where information in the protocol was incorrect or too vague to be identified with any one sentence in the text, although such cases were rare, the students' performances on the texts were coded on a 0-21 basis. based on 21 Carrell's idea units.. There were 40 items in reading comprehension passages which half point for each correct answer and 0 point for each incorrect answer were assigned.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

In order to test the hypotheses formulated in this study, a t-test (independent samples t-test and paired-sample t-test) and two way-ANOVA were utilized. T-test was used because there were two groups (EG and CG) and therefore two means, and because the most widely used statistical test for the comparison of two means is t-test. Paired-samples t-test (also referred to as repeated measures) was used because each group had pretest /posttest on three different occasions and there were three separate pairs in each group. Pretest/posttest experimental designs are an example of the type of situation

where this technique is appropriate. Finally, two way-ANOVA was applied because we had two independent variables (i.e., rhetorical organization and language proficiency) each with more than two levels (i.e., causative, descriptive texts of recall and reading comprehension passages). The level of significance was set at 0.1 and 99% degree of freedom was used.

3.6. The Place of Test Administration

As I mentioned before, there were three phases of testing: first, proficiency test was administered in one session to choose homogeneous subjects for experimental and control group. In this stage, proficiency test of PET was given to a population of sophomore participants majoring in English to choose 240 homogenous students. These 240 students randomly divided into two groups to take part in experiment. Then, a pretest of recall and reading comprehension administered to both control and experimental groups. The texts of recall were in the form of descriptive and causative. The passages for reading comprehension were selected from TBRT-GM module which included true-false, sentence-completion, outlining, Writer's-View Elicitation and skimming forms. The scores and mean of both control group and experimental group calculated and compared together through applying t-test, paired-samples t-test and two way- ANOVA. Finally, after two weeks explicit instruction of rhetorical organization to the experimental group the same tests of pretest were given as post-test. The stage of pretest performed in two sessions, one session for recall and one session for reading comprehension. The mean and SD of post-test and proficiency test of two groups (EG and CG) and different levels compared to investigate the impact of rhetorical organization explicit instruction on reading comprehension and recall of information in comparison with language proficiency. A recall protocol is a testing method. This has been the most common method employed in testing reading comprehension. The procedure was more likely to focus on the communication between text. The assumption was that recall indicates something about the readers' assimilation and reconstruction of text information and therefore reflected comprehension (Gambrel, Pefeiffer and Wilson, 1985). It required that the text be divided into idea units(e. g., Johnson, 1970; Meyer, 1975). An idea unit (also called a linguistic unit by Bransford

CHAPTER THREE: METHOD

and Franks, 1971, and Carrell, 1983, and information unit by Roller, 1990) is the smallest number of words necessary to express a thought idea. The participant read the text and his/her recall was measured and compared with the number of units in the original text. Comprehension was therefore measured by the amount of information in the response and test of reading comprehension. Recall scoring required the presence or absence of the gist of the text content. Reading comprehension scoring required the participants' answer to reading comprehension questions.

Validity and reliability of the reading test used

A Principle Component Factor Analysis was also performed to examine the construct validity of the TBRT-GM module--used for collecting the data on reading comprehension. The Varimax rotation method (with Kaiser Normalization) was used for this analysis. The scores of participants on each group of items were included in the analysis. Since five types of items were employed, a five-factor solution factor analysis was performed. The result of factor analysis showed that the item type loaded under each factor indicating the construct of these items. The results of factor analysis are presented in table 1 below.

As table 1 shows, two different types of items, i.e. skimming and True/False item type loaded under factor one. This may imply that the participants used a skimming strategy to answer True/False items, or vice versa. Factors 2, 3, and 4 show the construct of sentence-completion items, outlining items, and writer's view items, respectively.

Table 1:
Varimax Rotatin Factor Analysis for the Reading Comprehension Test

	Components				
	1	2	3	4	5
True-False					
.512				.490	
Sentence-Completion					
	.732				
Outlining					
		.868			
Writer's-View Elicitation					
			.727		
Skimming					
.781					

The reliability of the reading test is presented in table 2 below. The table shows that the reading test has good internal consistency, with a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.863. Table 2.

Reliability Statistics for the Reading Comprehension Test Used in the Study

Cronbach's Alpha coefficient	N of Items in the test
0.863	40

The recall protocol procedure has construct validity and reliability firmly a reader-based, constructivist model of L2 reading comprehension that has continued to evolve by Carrell and other researchers. PET proficiency test is also proved to be reliable and valid by an ample of researchers who applied it.

CHAPTER FOUR

Data Analysis and Interpretation

4.1. Introduction

In this chapter, restatement of the problem of this study will be presented, the data collection procedures will briefly be mentioned, and finally the data analysis with version 14 of SPSS software with result and discussions will be elaborated.

4.2. Restatement of the Problem

It was proposed that reading comprehension and recall of information are facilitated when rhetorical organization instructed explicitly and knowledge of rhetorical organization is a good predictor of reading comprehension and recall of information. The experiment conducted in the present research confirmed this. The study indicated explicit instruction of rhetorical organization enhanced reading comprehension and recall of information and knowledge of rhetorical organization was a good predictor of reading comprehension and recall of information.

4.3. Data Collection

As it was mentioned before, the participants were randomly assigned to two groups of 120 students each, based on the result of their proficiency test. One group functioned as

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

experimental and received rhetorical explicit instruction; the other group was the control one which received no explicit instruction. Both groups were given proficiency test of PET, the same pretest and posttest of recall and reading comprehension. The results of proficiency test for control and experimental groups were as follows:

	Subject Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Proficiency Test	Control Group	120	62.7000	12.58691	1.14902
	Experimental Group	120	61.5000	10.80383	.98625

4.3.1. Independent Samples T-Test for PET Results of Control and Experimental Groups (Alpha=0.01)

Independent samples t-test was conducted to compare a proficiency test of PET administered to a population of sophomore students at Azad University of Malayer. The following table 4.1 show the results of t-test.

Table 4.1
Group Statistics

	Subject Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Proficiency Test	Control Group	120	62.7000	12.58691	1.14902
	Experimental Group	120	61.5000	10.80383	.98625

Table 4.2
Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	
		F	Sig.
Proficiency Test	Equal variances assumed	2.446	.119
	Equal variances not assumed		

Table 4.2
Independent Samples Test

t-test for Equality of Means						
t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	99% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
.792	238	.429	1.20000	1.51425	-2.73196	5.13196
.792	232.654	.429	1.20000	1.51425	-2.73269	5.13269

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the mean scores of experimental and control groups. As it is shown in the table 4.1, there was not any significant difference in scores for control group (Mean= 62.70, SD=12.58) and experimental group (Mean= 61.50, SD= 10.80). $t(238) = .792, P > .01$. This results show that EG and CG were homogeneous. In the case of Levene's Test for equality of variances in table 4.2 Sig. > .01, so equal variances assumed for dependent variables and the assumption of equal variances has not been violated. The participants were randomly assigned to two groups (EG and CG). The magnitude of the differences in the means was very small (eta squared= .0026). According to the guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988), i.e., .01= small effect, .06= moderate effect, and .14= large effect. This result indicated that control group and experimental one were homogeneous concerning their means and SD. $t(238) = .792, P > .01$.

4.3.2. Independent Samples T-Test for PET Results of Control and Experimental Groups (Alpha=0.01)

A paired-samples t-test was conducted for both the control and experimental groups with alpha level 0.01. Paired-samples t-test is used when you have only one group of people and you collect data from them on two different occasions, or under two different conditions. Pretest/posttest experimental design is an example of the type of situation where this technique is appropriate. A paired-sample t-test also will tell you whether there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores for pretest and posttest in one group or experimental and control group.

4.3.3. Interpretation of output for paired-samples t-test

There are two steps involved in interpreting the result of this analysis.

Step1: determining overall significance

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

In the following tables labeled paired-samples t-test, there are three pair groups for control and experimental groups, each. Pretest and posttest were conducted on all pairs for control and experimental groups. These three pair groups consisted of: descriptive recall (pretest and posttest), causative recall (pretest and posttest) and reading (pretest and posttest). In the first pair of control group, as it is indicated in the table 4.3, Sig. = .144>.01, so there is not a significant difference between descriptive recall pretest and posttest in control group. Therefore, we can conclude that there was no significant difference in descriptive recall of control group or $t(119) = 1.47, P > 0.01$. Because there was not any explicit instruction of rhetorical organization for control group.

The same result as above was assumed for causative recall and reading pretests and posttests as follows:

Causative recall: $t(119) = -.844, P > 0.01$

Reading: $t(119) = -1.352, P > 0.01$

Step 2: comparing mean values

A paired-sample t-test was conducted for control group. There was not a statistically significant differences in means and Std. Deviation of pretest and posttest for three pairs. Descriptive recall pretest (mean= 71.19, SD= 10.74), Descriptive recall posttest (mean= 70.51 SD= 11.27); causative recall pretest (mean= 67.50, SD= 11.90), causative recall posttest (mean= 68.17, SD= 13.41); reading pretest (mean= 65.75, SD=12.58), reading pretest (mean= 66.04, SD=12.29).

But, for experimental group according to the following result in table 4.4, there was a significant difference between pretest and posttest in three pair groups so that the cited hypothesis, that is, explicit rhetorical organization instruction positively affects recall and comprehension, was accepted and the mentioned null hypothesis was safely rejected as follows:

Pair1: $t(119) = -22.07, P < 0.01$

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

ETA-squared= 0.8, This eta indicated a large effect size

Pair2: $t(119) = -26.04, P < 0.01$

ETA-squared= 0.85, This eta indicated a large effect size

Pair3: $t(119) = -16.13, P < 0.01$

ETA-squared= 0.68, This eta indicated a large effect size

Paired Samples Statistics Table 4.3

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Descriptive Recall (Pre-Test)	71.1905	120	10.7433	.9807
	Descriptive Recall (Post-Test)	70.5159	120	11.2703	1.0288
Pair 2	Causative Recall (Pre-Test)	67.5000	120	11.9014	1.0864
	Causative Recall (Post-Test)	68.1746	120	13.4118	1.2243
Pair 3	Reading (Pre-Test)	65.7500	120	12.5800	1.1484
	Reading (Post-Test)	66.0417	120	12.2970	1.1226

Table 4.3

Paired Samples Test for control group

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	99% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	Descriptive Recall (Pre-Test) - Descriptive Recall (Post-Test)	.6746	5.0265	.4589	-.5266	1.8758	1.470	119	.144
Pair 2	Causative Recall (Pre-Test) - Causative Recall (Post-Test)	-.6746	8.7587	.7996	-2.7677	1.4185	-.844	119	.401
Pair 3	Reading (Pre-Test) - Reading (Post-Test)	-.2917	2.3636	.2158	-.8565	.2732	1.352	119	.179

4.3.4. Paired-Samples T-Test for the Experimental Group with alpha level 0.01

Paired Samples Statistics Table 4.4

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Descriptive Recall (Pre-Test)	70.7143	120	10.7751	.9836
	Descriptive Recall (Post-Test)	79.1270	120	10.6064	.9682
Pair 2	Causative Recall (Pre-Test)	66.9048	120	10.8492	.9904
	Causative Recall (Post-Test)	74.7619	120	10.4875	.9574
Pair 3	Reading (Pre-Test)	64.5000	120	11.3278	1.0341
	Reading (Post-Test)	73.7083	120	10.7198	.9786

Table 4.4

Paired Samples Test for Experimental group

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	99% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	Descriptive Recall (Pre-Test) - Descriptive Recall (Post-Test)	-8.4127	4.1748	.3811	-9.4104	7.4150	22.074	119	.000
Pair 2	Causative Recall (Pre-Test) - Causative Recall (Post-Test)	-7.8571	3.3043	.3016	-8.6468	7.0675	26.048	119	.000
Pair 3	Reading (Pre-Test) - Reading (Post-Test)	-9.2083	6.2509	.5706	-10.7021	7.7146	16.137	119	.000

4.4. Mixed between-within Subjects ANOVA for Descriptive Recall and Proficiency Groups

A two way ANOVA was conducted to explore the impact of proficiency on the descriptive recall, causative recall texts and reading comprehension in comparison with the effect of rhetorical organization on these factors. Two- way ANOVA allows us to simultaneously test for the effect of two independent variables, that is, proficiency and rhetorical organization on the dependent variable, reading comprehension and recall of information, to identify any interaction effect. The subjects in this study were divided into four groups based on their proficiency levels. These four groups were (low, semi, fair, and high). As the following tables show, there was statistically strong significant difference of students' scores based on their proficiencies. In the table 4.5, the pretest descriptive recall mean scores of these four groups are as follows: low (mean=60.31, SD= 8.55), semi (mean= 68.48, SD=6.86), fair (mean= 75.71, SD= 7.42) and high (mean= 80.95, SD=6.98). In the case of posttest recall mean in table 4.5, there were four proficiency levels which consisted of low (mean=63.94, SD= 10.07), semi (mean= 74.52, SD=8.43), fair (mean= 77.22, SD= 9.92) and high (mean= 85.18, SD=7.32). There was statistically strong significant difference of students' scores based on their proficiencies. It is clear that in pretest and posttest the lowest mean score of descriptive recall was for low proficiency group and the highest for high proficiency group.

Descriptive Statistics Table 4.5

	Proficiency Level	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Descriptive Recall (Pre-Test)	Low	60.3175	8.5526	63
	Semi	68.4807	6.8650	63
	Fair	75.7143	7.4239	60
	High	80.9524	6.9839	54
	Total	70.9524	10.7393	240
Descriptive Recall (Post-Test)	Low	63.9456	10.0730	63
	Semi	74.5276	8.4303	63
	Fair	77.2222	9.9227	60
	High	85.1852	7.3228	54
	Total	74.8214	11.7419	240

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

In the "Multivariate Tests" box (table 4.6) the most commonly reported statistics is Wilk's Lambda. This value and associated probability value given in the column labeled Sig. are very important. In descriptive recall and proficiency the value for Wilk's Lambda was .726, with a probability value of .000 (which really means $P < .0001$). Because our P value was less than .01, we concluded that there was a statistically significant effect for descriptive recall. This indicated that there was a change in descriptive recall scores across four different levels. The main effect for levels was significant.

Table 4.6

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Eta Squared	Noncent Parameter	Observed Power (a)
DSCRPTV	Pillai's Trace	.274	89.224(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.274	89.224	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.726	89.224(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.274	89.224	1.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.378	89.224(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.274	89.224	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.378	89.224(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.274	89.224	1.000
DSCRPTV * PRFGRP	Pillai's Trace	.064	5.395(b)	3.000	236.000	.001	.064	16.186	.811
	Wilks' Lambda	.936	5.395(b)	3.000	236.000	.001	.064	16.186	.811
	Hotelling's Trace	.069	5.395(b)	3.000	236.000	.001	.064	16.186	.811
	Roy's Largest Root	.069	5.395(b)	3.000	236.000	.001	.064	16.186	.811

a Computed using alpha = .01

b Exact statistic

c Design: Intercept+PRFGRP

Within Subjects Design: DSCRPTV

As a result there was a significant effect for proficiency, Wilks' Lambda = .726, $F(1, 236) = 89.22$, $P < .01$, multivariate eta squared = .274. And, $F(3, 236) = 5.39$, $P < .01$.

4.4.1. Effect size

Although there was a statistically significant difference among the four levels of proficiency, it also needed to assess the effect size of this result. The value we are interested in is ETA squared, given in the "Multivariate Tests" output box in table 4.6 above. The value obtained for DSCRPTV in this study was .274. Using the commonly used guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988) (.01= small effect, .06= moderate effect and .14= large effect), this result suggested a very large effect size.

4.4.2. Interaction effect

In addition to the main effect, we are also interested to find out if there is a significant interaction effect. Is there the same change in scores for two different groups (pretest and posttest)? This is indicated in the second set of rows in the "Multivariate Tests" table (i.e. DSCRPTV PRFGRP). In this case the interaction effect was statistically significant (the Sig. level for Wilk' Lambda was .001, table 4.6 above, which was less than our alpha level of .01. This indicates that there is significant difference in the effect of proficiency on recall for pretest and post test.

We have explored the within-subjects effects, now we need to consider the main effect of our between-subjects variable.

4.4.3. Post-hoc tests

Although we know that our proficiency groups differ, we do not know where these differences occur: Is low group different to semi, fair or high, is semi group different to low, fair or high? And so on. To investigate these questions we need to conduct post-hoc tests. The results of post-hoc tests are provided in the table labeled "Multiple comparisons". In this case, Tukey HSD is one of the more commonly used tests. We look down the column labeled Sig. for any values less than .01. Significant results are also indicated by a little asterisk in the column labeled mean difference. In this study results are as follows in table 4.7.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

Multiple Comparisons table 4.7

Measure: MEASURE_1
Tukey HSD

(I) Proficiency Level	(J) Proficiency Level	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Low	Semi	-9.3726(*)	1.3710	.000	-13.6409	-5.1044
	Fair	-14.3367(*)	1.3880	.000	-18.6580	-10.0154
	High	-20.9373(*)	1.4270	.000	-25.3798	-16.4947
Semi	Low	9.3726(*)	1.3710	.000	5.1044	13.6409
	Fair	-4.9641(*)	1.3880	.002	-9.2854	-.6428
	High	-11.5646(*)	1.4270	.000	-16.0072	-7.1221
Fair	Low	14.3367(*)	1.3880	.000	10.0154	18.6580
	Semi	4.9641(*)	1.3880	.002	.6428	9.2854
	High	-6.6005(*)	1.4434	.000	-11.0941	-2.1070
High	Low	20.9373(*)	1.4270	.000	16.4947	25.3798
	Semi	11.5646(*)	1.4270	.000	7.1221	16.0072
	Fair	6.6005(*)	1.4434	.000	2.1070	11.0941

Based on observed means.

* The mean difference is significant at the .01 level.

In the above table Sig < .01 except for semi and fair. Therefore mean differences are significant for all groups, but semi and fair groups.

4.4.4. Plots

This plot is very useful for allowing us to visually inspect the relationship among our variables. This is often easier than trying to decipher a large table of numbers. The plots are often useful to inspect to help us better understand the impact of our two independent variables. In the plot, there is a large difference for high and low groups, but there is not a large difference in semi and fair groups. The results are indicated in the following graph.

The results of the analysis conducted above could be presented as follows:

A two-way between-within groups AVOVA was conducted to explore the impact of proficiency and rhetorical organization on descriptive recall, as by measured proficiency groups. Subjects were divided into four groups according to their proficiency level (low=63; semi=63; fair=60; high=54). There was a statistically significant main effect for proficiency Tests of Between Subjects Effect [$F(3,236) = 77.55, P = .000$], and the effect size was very big ($\eta^2 = .49$). Post-hoc comparison using the Tukey HSD test indicated that the pretest mean score for the low group ($M = 60.31, SD = 8.55$) was significantly different from the semi ($M = 68.48, SD = 6.86$), fair ($M = 75.71, SD = 7.42$), and high ($M = 80.92, SD = 6.98$) groups respectively. The same result is repeated for other groups comparison. And the posttest mean score for the low group ($M = 63.94, SD = 10.07$) was significantly different from the semi ($M = 74.52, SD = 8.43$), fair ($M = 77.22, SD = 9.92$), and high ($M = 85.18, SD = 7.32$) groups respectively. The same result is repeated for other groups comparison. The main effect for within subjects effect [$F(3,236) = 5.39, P = .001$], however the effect size was small ($\eta^2 = .06$). Wilks' Lambda = .726, $F(1, 236) = 89.22, P < .01$, multivariate $\eta^2 = .274$. And, $F(3, 236) = 5.39, P < .01, \eta^2 = .06$.

4.4.5. Between-subjects effect

The results that we need to look at are in the table labeled "Tests of Between-Subjects Effect" (table 4.8 below). Read across the row labeled PRFGRP (this is the shortened SPSS name for the level of proficiency). The Sig. value was .000. This was less than our alpha level of .01. Therefore, we concluded that the main effect for proficiency level was significant. There was significant difference in the descriptive recall scores for the four groups. Table 4.10 shows this result.

Table 4.8

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1
Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared
Intercept	2568315.471	1	2568315.471	21688.667	.000	.989
PRFGRP	27551.936	3	9183.979	77.556	.000	.496
Error	27946.505	236	118.417			

a. Computed using alpha = .01

4.4.6. Effect size

The effect size of the between-subject effect is also given in the tests of Between-Subjects Effect table. The ETA-squared value for PRFGRP in this case was .496 in table 4.8 above. This was very big. It is therefore not surprising that it reached statistical significance.

4.5. Mixed between-within Subjects ANOVA for Causative Recall and Proficiency Groups

The same interpretation as descriptive recall can be considered for causative recall, but the figures and sometimes significance are different, as follows:

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

In the table 4.9, the pretest causative recall mean scores of these four groups are as follows: low (mean=56.46, SD= 10.50), semi (mean= 64.85, SD=7.76), fair (mean= 70.71, SD= 6.83) and high (mean= 78.57, SD=6.45). In the case of posttest recall mean in table 4.12, there were four proficiency levels which consisted of low (mean=60.46, SD= 11.43), semi (mean= 69.91, SD=11.84), fair (mean= 76.42, SD= 8.05) and high (mean= 80.59, SD=7.51). There was statistically strong significant difference of students' scores based on their proficiencies. It is clear that in pretest and posttest the lowest mean score of causative recall was for low proficiency group and the highest for high proficiency.

table 4.9 **Descriptive Statistics**

	Proficiency Level	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Causative Recall (Pre-Test)	Low	56.4626	10.5047	63
	Semi	64.8526	7.7650	63
	Fair	70.7143	6.8377	60
	High	78.5714	6.4587	54
	Total	67.2024	11.3675	240
Causative Recall (Post-Test)	Low	60.4686	11.4310	63
	Semi	69.9169	11.8455	63
	Fair	76.4286	8.0557	60
	High	80.5996	7.1564	54
	Total	71.4683	12.4587	240

In the "Multivariate Tests" box (table 4.10) the most commonly reported statistics is Wilk's Lambda. This value and associated probability value given in the column labeled Sig. are very important. In causative recall and proficiency the value for Wilk's Lambda was .756, with a probability value of .000 (which really means $P < .0001$). Because our P value was less than .01, we concluded that there was a statistically significant effect for causative recall. This indicated that there was a change in causative recall scores across four different levels. The main effect for levels was significant

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

table 4.10
Multivariate Tests(c)

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Eta Squared
CAUSTV	Pillai's Trace	.244	76.182(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.244
	Wilks' Lambda	.756	76.182(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.244
	Hotelling's Trace	.323	76.182(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.244
	Roy's Largest Root	.323	76.182(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.244
CAUSTV * PRFGRP	Pillai's Trace	.033	2.650(b)	3.000	236.000	.050	.033
	Wilks' Lambda	.967	2.650(b)	3.000	236.000	.050	.033
	Hotelling's Trace	.034	2.650(b)	3.000	236.000	.050	.033
	Roy's Largest Root	.034	2.650(b)	3.000	236.000	.050	.033

a Computed using alpha = .01

b Exact statistic

c Design: Intercept+PRFGRP
 Within Subjects Design: CAUSTV

As a result there was a significant effect for proficiency, Wilks' Lambda= .756, $F(1, 236) = 76.18$, $P < .01$, multivariate eta squared = .244. And, $F(3, 236) = 2.65$, $P > .01$. CAUSTV PRFGRP was not significant.

4.5.1. Effect size

Although there was a statistically significant difference among the four levels of proficiency, it also needed to assess the effect size of this result. The value we are interested in is ETA squared, given in the "Multivariate Tests" output box in table 4.10 above. The value obtained for CAUSTV in this study was .244. Using the commonly used guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988) (.01= small effect, .06= moderate effect and .14= large effect), this result suggested a very large effect size.

4.5.2. Interaction effect

In addition to the main effect, we are also interested to find out if there is a significant interaction effect. Is there the same change in scores for two different groups (pretest and posttest)? This is indicated in the second set of rows in the "Multivariate Tests" table (i.e. CAUSTV PRFGRP). In this case the interaction effect was not statistically significant (the Sig. level for Wilk' Lambda was .05 which was greater than our alpha level of .01. This indicates that there is not significant difference in the effect of proficiency on recall for pre test and posttest. Table 4.11 indicates the result.

Table 4.11 **Multivariate Tests(c)**

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Eta Squared
CAUSTV	Pillai's Trace	.244	76.182(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.244
	Wilks' Lambda	.756	76.182(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.244
	Hotelling's Trace	.323	76.182(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.244
	Roy's Largest Root	.323	76.182(b)	1.000	236.000	.000	.244
CAUSTV * PRFGRP	Pillai's Trace	.033	2.650(b)	3.000	236.000	.050	.033
	Wilks' Lambda	.967	2.650(b)	3.000	236.000	.050	.033
	Hotelling's Trace	.034	2.650(b)	3.000	236.000	.050	.033
	Roy's Largest Root	.034	2.650(b)	3.000	236.000	.050	.033

We have explored the within-subjects effects, now we need to consider the main effect of our between-subjects variable.

4.5.3. Post-hoc tests

Although we know that our proficiency groups differ, we do not know where these differences occur: Is low group different to semi, fair or high, is semi group different to low, fair or high? And so on. To investigate these questions we need to conduct post-hoc tests. The results of post-hoc test are provided in the table labeled "Multiple comparisons". In this case, Tukey HSD is one of the more commonly used tests. We look down the column labeled Sig. for any values less than .01. Significant results are also indicated by a little asterisk in the column labeled mean difference. In this study results are as follows in table 4.12.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

table 4.12 Multiple Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1
Tukey HSD

(I) Proficiency Level	(J) Proficiency Level	Mean Difference (I- J)	Std. Error	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Low	Semi	-8.9191(*)	1.4751	.000	-13.5115	-4.3267
	Fair	-15.1058(*)	1.4934	.000	-19.7553	-10.4564
	High	-21.1199(*)	1.5353	.000	-25.8998	-16.3400
Semi	Low	8.9191(*)	1.4751	.000	4.3267	13.5115
	Fair	-6.1867(*)	1.4934	.000	-10.8361	-1.5373
	High	-12.2008(*)	1.5353	.000	-16.9807	-7.4209
Fair	Low	15.1058(*)	1.4934	.000	10.4564	19.7553
	Semi	6.1867(*)	1.4934	.000	1.5373	10.8361
	High	-6.0141(*)	1.5530	.001	-10.8489	-1.1794
High	Low	21.1199(*)	1.5353	.000	16.3400	25.8998
	Semi	12.2008(*)	1.5353	.000	7.4209	16.9807
	Fair	6.0141(*)	1.5530	.001	1.1794	10.8489

Based on observed means.

* The mean difference is significant at the .01 level.

4.5.4. Plots

This plot is very useful for allowing us to visually inspect the relationship among our variables. This is often easier than trying to decipher a large table of numbers. The plots are often useful to inspect to help us better understand the impact of our two independent variables. In the plot, there is a large difference for high and low groups, but there is not a large difference in high and fair groups. The results are indicated in the following graph.

The results of the analysis conducted above could be presented as follows:

A two-way between-within groups AVOVA was conducted to explore the impact of proficiency and rhetorical organization on causative recall, as by measured proficiency groups. Subjects were divided into four groups according to their proficiency level (low=63; semi=63; fair=60; high=54). There was a statistically significant main effect for proficiency Tests of Between Subjects Effect [$F(3,236) = 70.19, P = .000$], and the effect size was very big (eta squared = .47). Post-hoc comparison using the Tukey HSD test indicated that the pretest mean score for the low group ($M = 56.46, SD = 10.50$) was significantly different from the semi ($M = 64.58, SD = 7.76$), fair ($M = 70.71, SD = 6.83$), and high ($M = 78.57, SD = 6.645$) groups respectively. The same result is repeated for other groups comparison. And the posttest mean score for the low group ($M = 60.46, SD = 11.43$) was significantly different from the semi ($M = 69.91, SD = 11.84$), fair ($M = 76.42, SD = 8.05$), and high ($M = 80.59, SD = 7.15$) groups respectively. The same result is repeated for other groups comparison. The main effect for within subjects effect [$F(3,236) = 5.39, P = .05$], however the effect size was small (eta=.03). The main effect

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

for within subjects was not significant. Wilks' Lambda= .756, $F(1, 236) = 76.18$, $P < .01$, multivariate eta squared = .24. And, $F(3, 236) = 2.65$, $P > .01$, eta squared= .03.

4.5.5. Between-subjects effect

The results that we need to look at are in the table labeled "Tests of Between-Subjects Effect" in table 4.13. Read across the row labeled PRFGRP (this is the shortened SPSS variable name for the level of proficiency). The Sig. value was .000. This was less than our alpha level of .01. Therefore, we concluded that the main effect for proficiency level was significant. There was significant difference in the causative recall scores for the two groups (EG and CG).

Table 4.13 Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1
Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power(a)
Intercept	2326121.673	1	2326121.673	16968.597	.000	.986	16968.597	1.000
PRFGRP	28866.970	3	9622.323	70.193	.000	.472	210.579	1.000
Error	32351.804	236	137.084					

a. Computed using alpha = .01

4.5.6. Effect size

The effect size of the between-subject effect is also given in the tests of Between-Subjects Effect table. The ETA-squared value for PRFGRP in this case was .472 (table 4.13). This was very big. It is therefore not surprising that it reached statistical significance.

4.6. Mixed between-within Subjects ANOVA for Reading Comprehension and Proficiency Groups

The same interpretation as descriptive recall can be considered for reading, but the figures and sometimes significance are different, as follows:

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

In the table 4.14, the pretest reading mean scores of these four groups are as follows: low (mean=53.46 SD= 10.48), semi (mean= 61.66, SD=8.13), fair (mean= 70.25, SD= 6.47) and high (mean= 77.50, SD=4.52). In the case of posttest reading mean in table 4.17, there were four proficiency levels which consisted of low (mean=59.04, SD= 12.34), semi (mean= 68.33, SD=8.32), fair (mean= 73.58, SD= 8.97) and high (mean= 80.18, SD=7.00). There was statistically strong significant difference of students' scores based on their proficiencies. It is clear that in pretest and posttest the lowest mean score of reading was for low proficiency group and the highest for high proficiency.

Descriptive Statistics table 4.14

	Proficiency Level	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Reading (Pre-Test)	Low	53.0952	10.4892	63
	Semi	61.6667	8.1320	63
	Fair	70.2500	6.4719	60
	High	77.5000	4.5298	54
	Total	65.1250	11.9616	240
Reading (Post-Test)	Low	59.0476	12.3412	63
	Semi	68.3333	8.3280	63
	Fair	73.5833	8.9770	60
	High	80.1852	7.0015	54
	Total	69.8750	12.1353	240

In the "Multivariate Tests" box (table 4.15) the most commonly reported statistics is Wilk's Lambda. This value and associated probability value given in the column labeled Sig. are very important. In reading and proficiency the value for Wilk's Lambda was .325, with a probability value of .000 (which really means $P < .0001$). Because our P value was less than .01, we concluded that there was a statistically significant effect for reading. This indicated that there was a change in reading scores across four different levels. The main effect for levels was significant.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

table 4.15 **Multivariate Tests(c)**

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.
READNG	Pillai's Trace	.355	130.133(b)	1.000	236.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.645	130.133(b)	1.000	236.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.551	130.133(b)	1.000	236.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.551	130.133(b)	1.000	236.000	.000
READNG * PRFGRP	Pillai's Trace	.067	5.626(b)	3.000	236.000	.001
	Wilks' Lambda	.933	5.626(b)	3.000	236.000	.001
	Hotelling's Trace	.072	5.626(b)	3.000	236.000	.001
	Roy's Largest Root	.072	5.626(b)	3.000	236.000	.001

a Computed using alpha = .01

b Exact statistic

c Design: Intercept+PRFGRP

Within Subjects Design: READNG

Multivariate Tests(c)

Effect		Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power(a)
READNG	Pillai's Trace	.355	130.133	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.355	130.133	1.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.355	130.133	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.355	130.133	1.000
READNG * PRFGRP	Pillai's Trace	.067	16.879	.833
	Wilks' Lambda	.067	16.879	.833
	Hotelling's Trace	.067	16.879	.833
	Roy's Largest Root	.067	16.879	.833

a Computed using alpha = .01

b Exact statistic

c Design: Intercept+PRFGRP

Within Subjects Design: READNG

As a result there was a significant effect for proficiency, Wilks' Lambda= .645, F (1, 236) = 130.13, P< .01, multivariate eta squared = .355 And, F(3, 236) = 5.62, P< .01. READNG PRFGRP was significant.

4.6.1. Effect size

Although there was a statistically significant difference among the four levels of proficiency, it also needed to assess the effect size of this result. The value we are interested in is ETA squared, given in the "Multivariate Tests" output box in table 4.15 above.

The value obtained for DSCRPTV in this study was .274. Using the commonly used guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988) (.01= small effect, .06= moderate effect and .14= large effect), this result suggested a very large effect size.

4.6.2. Interaction effect

In addition to the main effect, we are also interested to find out if there is a significant interaction effect. Is there the same change in scores for two different groups (pretest and posttest)? This is indicated in the second set of rows in the "Multivariate Tests" table (i.e. READNG PRFGRP). In this case the interaction effect was statistically significant (the Sig. level for Wilk' Lambda was .001, table 4.15 above, which was less than our alpha level of .01. This indicates that there is significant difference in the effect of proficiency on reading for pretest and post test.

We have explored the within-subjects effects, now we need to consider the main effect of our between-subjects variable.

4.6.3. Post-hoc tests

Although we know that our proficiency groups differ, we do not know where these differences occur: Is low group different to semi, fair or high, is semi group different to low, fair or high? And so on. To investigate these questions we need to conduct post-hoc tests. The results of post-hoc test are provided in the table labeled "Multiple comparisons". In this case, Tukey HSD is one of the more commonly used tests. We look down the column labeled Sig. for any values less than .01. Significant results are also indicated by a little asterisk in the column labeled mean difference. In this study results are as follows in table 4.16.

Post Hoc Tests Proficiency Level
Multiple Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

table 4.16

Tukey HSD

(I) Proficiency Level	(J) Proficiency Level	Mean Difference (I- J)	Std. Error	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Low	Semi	-8.9286(*)	1.4409	.000	-13.4145	-4.4426
	Fair	-15.8452(*)	1.4588	.000	-20.3869	-11.3035
	High	-22.7712(*)	1.4998	.000	-27.4403	-18.1020
Semi	Low	8.9286(*)	1.4409	.000	4.4426	13.4145
	Fair	-6.9167(*)	1.4588	.000	-11.4584	-2.3750
	High	-13.8426(*)	1.4998	.000	-18.5117	-9.1734
Fair	Low	15.8452(*)	1.4588	.000	11.3035	20.3869
	Semi	6.9167(*)	1.4588	.000	2.3750	11.4584
	High	-6.9259(*)	1.5170	.000	-11.6486	-2.2032
High	Low	22.7712(*)	1.4998	.000	18.1020	27.4403
	Semi	13.8426(*)	1.4998	.000	9.1734	18.5117
	Fair	6.9259(*)	1.5170	.000	2.2032	11.6486

Based on observed means.

* The mean difference is significant at the .01 level.

4.6.4. Plots

This plot is very useful for allowing us to visually inspect the relationship among our variables. This is often easier than trying to decipher a large table of numbers. The plots are often useful to inspect to help us better understand the impact of our two independent variables. In the plot, there is a large difference for high and low groups, but there is not a large difference in high and fair groups. The results are indicated in the following graph.

The results of the analysis conducted above could be presented as follows:

A two-way between-within groups AVOVA was conducted to explore the impact of proficiency and rhetorical organization on causative recall, as measured by proficiency groups. Subjects were divided into four groups according to their proficiency level (low=63; semi=63; fair=60; high=54). There was a statistically significant main effect for proficiency Tests of Between Subjects Effect [$F(3,236) = 85.31, P = .000$], and the effect size was very big ($\eta^2 = .52$). Post-hoc comparison using the Tukey HSD test indicated that the pretest mean score for the low group (mean=53.09, SD= 10.48), semi (mean= 61.66, SD=8.13), fair (mean= 70.25, SD= 6.47) and high (mean= 77.50, SD=4.52). In the case of posttest reading mean in table 4.21, there were four proficiency levels which consisted of low (mean=59.04, SD= 12.34), semi (mean= 68.33, SD=8.32), fair (mean= 73.58, SD= 8.97) and high (mean= 80.18, SD=7.00) groups respectively. The same result is repeated for other groups comparison. The main effect for within subjects effect [$F(3,236) = 13.13, P = .000$], however the effect size was small ($\eta = .06$). The main effect for within subjects was not significant.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

Wilks' Lambda= .645, $F(1, 236) = 130.13$, $P < .01$, multivariate eta squared = .35. And, $F(3, 236) = 5.62$, $P < .01$, eta squared= .06.

4.6.5. Between-subjects effect

The results that we need to look at are in the table labeled "Tests of Between-Subjects Effect". Read across the row labeled PRFGRP (this is the shortened SPSS variable name for the level of proficiency). The Sig. value was .000. This was less than our alpha level of .01. Therefore, we concluded that the main effect for proficiency level was significant. There was significant difference in the causative recall scores for the two groups (EG and CG). Table 4.17.

Table 4.17 Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1
Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared
Intercept	2207995.797	1	2207995.797	16880.129	.000	.986
PRFGRP	33480.152	3	11160.051	85.319	.000	.520
Error	30869.848	236	130.804			

a. Computed using alpha = .01

Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power(a)
Intercept	2207995.797	16880.129	1.000
PRFGRP	33480.152	255.956	1.000
Error	30869.848		

a. Computed using alpha = .01

4.6.6. Effect size

The effect size of the between-subject effect is also given in the tests of Between-Subjects Effect table. The ETA-squared value for PRFGRP in this case was .520 in table 4.17. This was very big. It is therefore not surprising that it reached statistical significance.

4.7. Mixed between-within ANOVA for Descriptive Recall and Experimental VS Control Groups

The use of both between-subjects design (comparing two or more different groups), and within –subjects or repeated measures designs (one group of subjects exposed to two or more conditions). These approaches may be treated separately or may be combined in the one study as this one, with one independent variable being between-subjects, and the other a within-subjects variable. In this study, the researcher investigated the impact of rhetorical organization on EFL students' reading comprehension and recall of information (using pretest and posttest) for both control and experimental groups. In this case, there was two independent variables, one was a between-subjects variable (instruction of rhetorical organization for experimental group and no instruction for control group), the other variable was a within-subjects (the role of rhetorical organization or language proficiency on recall and reading comprehension).

Version 14 of SPSS software allowed the researcher to combine between-subjects and within-subjects variables in the one analysis. This analysis referred in Cohen (1988) as split-plot ANOVA design (SPANOVA). Students were divided into two equal groups. One (EG) was given a number of sessions instruction, designed to improve their rhetorical organization, the second group (CG) received no explicit instruction. There were two control and experimental groups which performed the same pretest and post of recall and reading comprehension. Recall tests were in the form of descriptive and causative rhetorical organization. There was explicit instruction of rhetorical organization for experimental group after pretest, but the control group received no instruction.

As it is indicated in "Descriptive Statistics" table 4.18:

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

table 4.18 Descriptive Statistics

	Subject Groups	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Descriptive Recall (Pre-Test)	Control Group	71.1905	10.7433	120
	Experimental Group	70.7143	10.7751	120
	Total	70.9524	10.7393	240
Descriptive Recall (Post-Test)	Control Group	70.5159	11.2703	120
	Experimental Group	79.1270	10.6064	120
	Total	74.8214	11.7419	240

The above results showed that the mean of experimental posttest changed meaningfully to support the hypothesis for descriptive recall. In order to reject the H0 in the "Multivariate Tests" box table 4.19 the most commonly reported statistic, that is, Wilks' Lambda and associated probability value in the column labeled Sig. were concerned. In this study, the value for Wilks' Lambda was .586, with a probability value of .000 (which really means $P < .0001$). Because our P value was less than .01, we concluded that there was a statistically significant effect of rhetorical organization explicit instruction on descriptive recall. This suggested that there was a change in descriptive recall scores after rhetorical instruction. The effect size of this result indicated in ETA-squared value, given in the "Multivariate Tests" output box ($\eta^2 = .414$). Using the commonly used guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988), .01= small effect, .06= moderate effect, .14= large effect, this result suggests a very large effect size. $F(1,238) = 168.29$, $P < .01$.

table 4.19 Multivariate Tests(c)

Effect		Value	F	Hypot thesis df	Error df	Sig.	Eta Squar ed
DSCRPTV	Pillai's Trace	.414	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
	Wilks' Lambda	.586	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
	Hotelling's Trace	.707	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
	Roy's Largest Root	.707	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
DSCRPTV * GROUPS	Pillai's Trace	.494	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494
	Wilks' Lambda	.506	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494
	Hotelling's Trace	.975	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494
	Roy's Largest Root	.975	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494

a Computed using alpha = .01

b Exact statistic

c Design: Intercept+GROUPS

Within Subjects Design: DSCRPTV

4.7. 1. Interaction effect

In addition to the main effect, we are also interested to find out if there is a significant interaction effect. Is there the same change in scores for two different groups (pretest and posttest)? This is indicated in the second set of rows in the "Multivariate Tests" table 4.20 (i.e. DSCRPTV GROUPS). In this case the interaction effect was statistically significant (the Sig. level for Wilk' Lambda was .000 which was less than our alpha level of .01). $F(1,238) = 232, P < .01$.

Multivariate Tests(c) table 4.20

Effect		Value	F	Hypot hesis df	Error df	Sig.	Eta Squared
DSCRPTV	Pillai's Trace	.414	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
	Wilks' Lambda	.586	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
	Hotelling's Trace	.707	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
	Roy's Largest Root	.707	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
DSCRPTV * GROUPS	Pillai's Trace	.494	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494
	Wilks' Lambda	.506	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494
	Hotelling's Trace	.975	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494
	Roy's Largest Root	.975	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494

a Computed using alpha = .01
 b Exact statistic
 c Design: Intercept+GROUPS
 Within Subjects Design: DSCRPTV

We have explored the within-subjects effects, now we need to consider the main effect of our between-subjects variable.

4.7. 2. Between-subjects effect

The results that we need to look at are in the table 4.21 labeled "Tests of Between-Subjects Effect". Read across the row labeled GROUPS (this is the shortened SPSS variable name for the level of proficiency). The Sig. value was .003. This was less than our alpha level of .01. Therefore, we concluded that the main effect for proficiency

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

level was significant. There was significant difference in the descriptive recall scores for the two groups (EG and CG).

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects table 4.21

Measure: MEASURE_1

Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared
Intercept	2550000.425	1	2550000.425	11341.143	.000	.979
GROUPS	1985.308	1	1985.308	8.830	.003	.036
Error	53513.133	238	224.845			

a. Computed using alpha = .01

4.7. 3. Effect size

The effect size of the between-subjects effect is also given in the Tests of Between-Subjects Effect table 4.21. The ETA-squared value for GROUPS in this case was .036. Using the commonly used guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988), .01= small effect, .06= moderate effect, .14= large effect, this result suggests a small effect size difference in the descriptive recall scores.

4.7. 4. Plots

This plot is very useful for allowing us to visually inspect the relationship among our variables. This is often easier than trying to decipher a large table of numbers. The plots are often useful to inspect to help us better understand the impact of our two independent variables. In this plot, there is a large difference for high and low groups, but there is not a large difference in semi and fair groups. The results are indicated in the following graph.

The results of the analysis conducted above could be presented as follows:

A one-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to compare scores effect of rhetorical organization on descriptive recall through pretest and posttest. The means and standard deviations are presented in table 4.22. There was a significant effect for experimental group in table 4.23, Wilks' Lambda = .586, $F(1,238) = 168.29$, $P < .01$.

table 4.22 **Descriptive Statistics**

	Subject Groups	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Descriptive Recall (Pre-Test)	Control Group	71.1905	10.7433	120
	Experimental Group	70.7143	10.7751	120
	Total	70.9524	10.7393	240
Descriptive Recall (Post-Test)	Control Group	70.5159	11.2703	120
	Experimental Group	79.1270	10.6064	120
	Total	74.8214	11.7419	240

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

table 4.23 **Multivariate Tests(c)**

Effect		Value	F	Hypot thesis df	Error df	Sig.	Eta Squ are d
DSCRPTV	Pillai's Trace	.414	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
	Wilks' Lambda	.586	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
	Hotelling's Trace	.707	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
	Roy's Largest Root	.707	168.296(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.414
DSCRPTV * GROUPS	Pillai's Trace	.494	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494
	Wilks' Lambda	.506	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494
	Hotelling's Trace	.975	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494
	Roy's Largest Root	.975	232.100(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.494

A two-way between groups AVOVA was conducted to explore the impact of rhetorical organization on descriptive recall, as measured by experimental and control groups. Subjects were divided into two groups (Experimental and Control). There was a statistically significant main effect for experimental group [F (1,238) = 8.83, P= .003], and the effect size was small (eta squared = .03). They are presented in table 4.24.

table 4.24 **Tests of Between-Subjects Effects**

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared
Intercept	2550000.425	1	2550000.425	11341.143	.000	.979
GROUPS	1985.308	1	1985.308	8.830	.003	.036
Error	53513.133	238	224.845			

a. Computed using alpha = .01

4.8. Mixed between-within ANOVA for Causative Recall and Experimental VS Control Groups

The use of both between-subjects design (comparing two or more different groups), and within –subjects or repeated measures designs (one group of subjects exposed to two or more conditions). These approaches may be treated separately or may be combined in

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

the one study as this one, with one independent variable being between-subjects, and the other a within-subjects variable. In this study, the researcher investigated the impact of rhetorical organization on EFL students' reading comprehension and recall of information (using pretest and posttest) for both control and experimental groups. In this case, there was two independent variables, one was a between-subjects variable (instruction of rhetorical organization for experimental group and no instruction for control group), the other variable was a within-subjects (the role of rhetorical organization or language proficiency on recall and reading comprehension).

Version 14 of SPSS software allowed the researcher to combine between-subjects and within-subjects variables in the one analysis. This analysis referred in Cohen (1988) as split-plot ANOVA design (SPANOVA). Students were divided into two equal groups. One (EG) was given a number of sessions instruction, designed to improve their rhetorical organization, the second group (CG) received no explicit instruction. There were two control and experimental groups which performed the same pretest and post of recall and reading comprehension. Recall tests were in the form of descriptive and causative rhetorical organization. There was explicit instruction of rhetorical organization for experimental group after pretest, but the control group received no instruction. As it is indicated in "Descriptive Statistics" table 4.25:

Descriptive Statistics
table 4.25

	Subject Groups	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Causative Recall (Pre-Test)	Control Group	67.5000	11.9014	120
	Experimental Group	66.9048	10.8492	120
	Total	67.2024	11.3675	240
Causative Recall (Post-Test)	Control Group	68.1746	13.4118	120
	Experimental Group	74.7619	10.4875	120
	Total	71.4683	12.4587	240

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

The above results showed that the mean of experimental posttest changed meaningfully to support the first hypothesis for causative recall. In order to reject the first H0 in the "Multivariate Tests" box table 4.26 the most commonly reported statistic, that is, Wilks' Lambda and associated probability value in the column labeled Sig. were concerned. In this study, the value for Wilks' Lambda was .705, with a probability value of .000 (which really means $P < 0.001$). Because our P value was less than .01, we concluded that there was a statistically significant effect of rhetorical organization explicit instruction on causative recall. This suggested that that there was a change in causative recall scores after rhetorical instruction. The effect size of this result indicated in ETA-squared value, given in the "Multivariate Tests" output box ($\eta^2 = .295$). Using the commonly used guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988), .01= small effect, .06= moderate effect, .14= large effect, this result suggests a very large effect size. $F(1,238) = 99.67$, $P < .01$.

table 4.26 Multivariate Tests(c)

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.
CAUSTV	Pillai's Trace	.295	99.675(b)	1.000	238.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.705	99.675(b)	1.000	238.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.419	99.675(b)	1.000	238.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.419	99.675(b)	1.000	238.000	.000
CAUSTV * GROUPS	Pillai's Trace	.229	70.643(b)	1.000	238.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.771	70.643(b)	1.000	238.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.297	70.643(b)	1.000	238.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.297	70.643(b)	1.000	238.000	.000

Multivariate Tests(c)

Effect		Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power(a)
CAUSTV	Pillai's Trace	.295	99.675	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.295	99.675	1.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.295	99.675	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.295	99.675	1.000
CAUSTV * GROUPS	Pillai's Trace	.229	70.643	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.229	70.643	1.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.229	70.643	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.229	70.643	1.000

a Computed using alpha = .01

b Exact statistic

c Design: Intercept+GROUPS

Within Subjects Design: CAUSTV

4.8. 1. Interaction effect

In addition to the main effect, we are also interested to find out if there is a significant interaction effect. Is there the same change in scores for two different groups (pretest and posttest)? This is indicated in the second set of rows in the "Multivariate Tests" table 4.26 (i.e. CAUSTV GRIUPS). In this case the interaction effect was statistically significant (the Sig. level for Wilk' Lambda was .000 which was less than our alpha level of .01). $F(1,238) = 70.64, P < .01$.

4.8. 2. Between-subjects effect

The results that we need to look at are in the table 4.27 labeled "Tests of Between-Subjects Effect". Read across the row labeled GROUPS (this is the shortened SPSS variable name for the level of proficiency). The Sig. value was .04. This was more than our alpha level of .01. Therefore, we concluded that the main effect for proficiency level was not significant. There was not significant difference in the causative recall scores for the two groups (EG and CG).

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects table 4.27

Measure: MEASURE_1
Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared
Intercept	2307545.399	1	2307545.399	9131.708	.000	.975
GROUPS	1077.145	1	1077.145	4.263	.040	.018
Error	60141.629	238	252.696			

a. Computed using alpha = .01

4.8. 3. Effect size

The effect size of the between-subjects effect is also given in the Tests of Between-Subjects Effect table 4.30. The ETA-squared value for GROUPS in this case was .018. Using the commonly used guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988), .01= small effect, .06= moderate effect, .14= large effect, this result suggests a small effect size.

4.8. 4. Plots

This plot is very useful for allowing us to visually inspect the relationship among our variables. This is often easier than trying to decipher a large table of numbers. The plots are often useful to inspect to help us better understand the impact of our independent variable. In this plot, there is a large difference for experimental and control groups in posttest, but there is not a large difference for experimental and control groups in pretest. The results are indicated in the following graph.

The results of the analysis conducted above could be presented as follows:

A one-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to compare scores effect of rhetorical organization on causative recall through pretest and posttest. The means and standard deviations are presented in table 4.28. There was a significant effect for experimental group, Wilks' Lambda = .705, $F(1,238) = 99.67$, $P < .01$.

	Subject Groups	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Causative Recall (Pre-Test)	Control Group	67.5000	11.9014	120
	Experimental Group	66.9048	10.8492	120
	Total	67.2024	11.3675	240
Causative Recall (Post-Test)	Control Group	68.1746	13.4118	120
	Experimental Group	74.7619	10.4875	120
	Total	71.4683	12.4587	240

table 4.28

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

table 4.28 **Multivariate Tests(c)**

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Eta Squared
CAUSTV	Pillai's Trace	.295	99.675(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.295
	Wilks' Lambda	.705	99.675(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.295
	Hotelling's Trace	.419	99.675(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.295
	Roy's Largest Root	.419	99.675(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.295
CAUSTV * GROUPS	Pillai's Trace	.229	70.643(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.229
	Wilks' Lambda	.771	70.643(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.229
	Hotelling's Trace	.297	70.643(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.229
	Roy's Largest Root	.297	70.643(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.229

A two-way between groups AVOVA was conducted to explore the impact of rhetorical organization on causative recall, as measured by experimental and control groups. Subjects were divided into two groups (Experimental and Control). There was a statistically significant main effect for experimental group [$F(1,238) = 4.26, P = .04$], and the effect size was small (eta squared = .01). They are presented in table 4.29.

table 4.29 **Tests of Between-Subjects Effects**

Measure: MEASURE_1
Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared
Intercept	2307545.399	1	2307545.399	9131.708	.000	.975
GROUPS	1077.145	1	1077.145	4.263	.040	.018
Error	60141.629	238	252.696			

a. Computed using alpha = .01

4.9. Mixed between-within ANOVA for Reading Comprehension and Experimental VS Control Groups

As it is indicated in "Descriptive Statistics" table 4.30, "Reading Comprehension" (Pre-Test) is as follows:

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

table 4.30 Descriptive Statistics

	Subject Groups	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Reading (Pre-Test)	Control Group	65.7500	12.5800	120
	Experimental Group	64.5000	11.3278	120
	Total	65.1250	11.9616	240
Reading (Post-Test)	Control Group	66.0417	12.2970	120
	Experimental Group	73.7083	10.7198	120
	Total	69.8750	12.1353	240

The above results showed that the mean of experimental posttest changed meaningfully to support the first hypothesis for reading comprehension. In order to reject the first H0 in the "Multivariate Tests" box the most commonly reported statistic, that is, Wilks' Lambda and associated probability value in the column labeled Sig. were concerned. In this study, the value for Wilks' Lambda was .495, with a probability value of .000 (which really means $P < .01$). Because our P value was less than .01, we concluded that there was a statistically significant effect of rhetorical organization explicit instruction on reading comprehension. This suggested that that there was a change in reading comprehension scores after rhetorical instruction. The effect size of this result indicated in ETA-squared value, given in the "Multivariate Tests" output box table 4.31 ($\eta^2 = .495$). Using the commonly used guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988), .01= small effect, .06= moderate effect, .14= large effect, this result suggests a very large effect size. $F(1,238) = 242.49, P < .01$.

table 4.31 Multivariate Tests(c)

Effect		Value	F	Hypot hesis df	Error df	Sig.	Eta Squared
READNG	Pillai's Trace	.505	242.497(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.505
	Wilks' Lambda	.495	242.497(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.505
	Hotelling's Trace	1.019	242.497(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.505
	Roy's Largest Root	1.019	242.497(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.505
READNG * GROUPS	Pillai's Trace	.473	213.631(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.473
	Wilks' Lambda	.527	213.631(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.473
	Hotelling's Trace	.898	213.631(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.473
	Roy's Largest Root	.898	213.631(b)	1.000	238.000	.000	.473

a Computed using alpha = .01

b Exact statistic

c Design: Intercept+GROUPS

Within Subjects Design: READNG

4.9. 1. Interaction effect

In addition to the main effect, we are also interested to find out if there is a significant interaction effect. Is there the same change in scores for two different groups (pretest and posttest)? This is indicated in the second set of rows in the "Multivariate Tests" table 4.31 (i.e. READNG GROUPS). In this case the interaction effect was statistically significant (the Sig. level for Wilk' Lambda was .000 which was less than our alpha level of .01).

4.9. 2. Between-subjects effect

The results that we need to look at are in the table labeled "Tests of Between-Subjects Effect". Read across the row labeled GROUPS (this is the shortened SPSS variable name for the level of proficiency). The Sig. value was .032 in table 4.32. This was more than our alpha level of .01. Therefore, we concluded that the main effect for proficiency level was not significant. There was not significant difference in the reading comprehension scores for the two groups (EG and CG).

table 4.32 Tests of Between-Subjects Effect

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared
Intercept	2187000.000	1	2187000.000	8246.973	.000	.972
GROUPS	1235.208	1	1235.208	4.658	.032	.019
Error	63114.792	238	265.188			

4.9. 3. Effect size

The effect size of the between-subjects effect is also given in the Tests of Between-Subjects Effect table 4.32. The ETA-squared value for GROUPS in this case was .019. Using the commonly used guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988), .01= small effect, .06= moderate effect, .14= large effect, this result suggests a small effect size.

4.9. 4. Plots

This plot is very useful for allowing us to visually inspect the relationship among our variables. This is often easier than trying to decipher a large table of numbers. The plots are often useful to inspect to help us better understand the impact of our independent variable. In this plot, there is a large difference for experimental and control groups in posttest, but there is not a large difference for experimental and control groups in pretest. The results are indicated in the following graph.

CHAPTER FIVE

Conclusion, Pedagogical Implications and Suggestions for Further Research

5.1. Introduction

There are three parts in this chapter that in the first part restatement of the hypothesis and an overview of the procedure followed for the study will be presented. In the second part, pedagogical implications will be examined, and in the third part of this chapter suggestions for further research will be dealt with.

5.2. Restatement of the Hypothesis

The specific aim of this study, stated in the form of a hypothesis, was to investigate if different rhetorical organizations affected comprehension and recall of information, and knowledge of rhetorical organization was a good predictor of comprehension and

recall. In order to manipulate the hypothesis of the study, 240 homogeneous students from Azad University of Malayer randomly assigned as experimental and control groups. According to proficiency test of PET these two groups were homogeneous on the part of their mean and standard deviation, chapter four (table 4.1). A pretest of descriptive and causative recall and reading comprehension administered for two groups. Based on statistical results obtained from different levels of recall and reading comprehension, there was not significant differences between control and experimental group in pretest (tables 4.3, 4.4, 4.26 and 4.31) in chapter four indicate these results.

When the results of pretest in different levels became clear, the stage of explicit instruction of rhetorical organization for experimental group started and lasted for two weeks. During this time control group received no instruction of rhetorical organization, but they follow the ordinary activities of their education. In order to make the experimental group familiar with the concept of rhetorical organization and organizational patterns used in the texts, two units (eight and ten) of the book of advanced writing (1383) which had to do with descriptive and causative patterns were taught in the classroom. There were some descriptive and causative patterns in these two units (eight and ten) which were analyzed and clarified in the classroom. Moreover, the descriptive and causative rhetorical patterns of a few articles such as Carrell (1987), Sharp (2002), and Martinez (2002) were delivered and analyzed in the classroom.

Finally, both groups (EG and CG) received two post-tests the same as pretests. Then, the scores which obtained from pretests and posttests compared in terms of their means to see the effect of rhetorical organization instruction on recall and reading comprehension and compared the effect of rhetorical organization instruction with language proficiency as predictors on reading comprehension and recall of information .The researcher performed t-test, paired-samples t-test and a two-way ANOVA on the results of both post-tests.

CHAPTER FIVE: Conclusion, Pedagogical Implications and.....

Analyses of the recall protocols and reading comprehension tables based on above test techniques in chapter four revealed that the experimental group outperformed the control group in the number of idea units recall and reading comprehension in all descriptive, causative and reading comprehension posttests. But there was no significant difference between experimental and control groups in descriptive, causative and reading comprehension pretests. Because the experimental group underwent detailed instruction in the rhetorical organization of the classification, causative and descriptive type text structures. Moreover, according to the mean scores of recall for descriptive and causative, the subjects recall more idea units in descriptive texts rather causative one.

5.3. Pedagogical Implications

Implications for teaching and materials development: If convincing evidence was found that text arrangement with the so-called rhetorical organization, was helpful in increasing comprehension and retrieval, teachers and university instructors will benefit from the results. They will present their content materials based on such a hypothesis to facilitate the comprehension and recall of the idea units covered, in other words, if it happened that the outcome of this research revealed any significant difference between the amounts of idea units recalled and a better comprehension occurred from the passages awareness of rhetorical organization, text preparation and content presentation should follow the findings by providing readers with texts in such orders of rhetorical organization which enhance later retrieval of the idea units and comprehension of the texts. Moreover, description text was found to be significantly easier for all proficiency or ability groups. This result may be of benefit for both theoretical and pedagogical consideration. Theoreticians may come up with new and better methods for teaching reading, or recall of information by providing more descriptive texts, , and practitioners may sue more organization of the descriptive type of text as an important factor in reading comprehension and recall of information.

Thus, I make a proposal for teaching reading comprehension to students based on the conscious use of structure understood as the interpretation of the rhetorical information and of its predictive function.

5.4. Suggestions for Further Research

Language is a complex phenomenon that nobody is able to cover all aspects of it. Specifically, in the case of comprehension and recall in relation to rhetorical organization there are ample of researches which no one is complete to cover all aspects of this specific problem. Therefore, always some new questions and statement problems arise that I suggest some of them.

1. Further research into this topic should consider using larger samples and more comprehensive assessment procedures than has been the norm in the past.
2. Further research should also consider extending the range of rhetorical patterns beyond the two patterns looked at here. Longer texts which contain more varied patterns within each text might also be considered.
3. Comparison among different language groups and the possible effects of how differing rhetorical organizations relate to the students' mother tongue offer considerable scope for further research.
4. This study does not distinguish between the genders, whether male readers are more talent in comprehension and production based on the recognition of rhetorical organization or females, so further research in this domain is suggested.
5. Do simultaneous conscious recognition of rhetorical organization and reproduction by the reader have a positive effect on reading comprehension?
6. The experiment focused on EFL students. A similar study can be carried out to investigate the effect of rhetorical organization on ESP or high school students.

CHAPTER FIVE: Conclusion, Pedagogical Implications and.....

7. The present study was limited to reading. It would be interesting to conduct a similar experiment with other skills, such as writing and listening.